

Automated Train Pass-by Classification Using Self-Supervised Transformers

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Abstract—Railway noise pollution motivates automatic, event-level analysis of individual train pass-bys. This work studies the representation-learning problem underlying the classification of segmented railway sound events. In this setting, existing approaches remain convolution-based, and transformer encoders as well as transfer-learning strategies have not been systematically evaluated. On the ADSiM railway-sound dataset, two self-supervised objectives: Audio-MAE and contrastive triplet learning, are compared on a ViT-Base encoder. The datasets AudioSet and ImageNet are used as additional external transfer-learning sources, either for direct encoder-weight initialisation or as starting points for continued in-domain pretraining. All comparisons follow a dual-split, multi-seed protocol with the macro-averaged F1-score (macro-F1) as the primary metric and mean average precision (mAP) as the secondary metric. The ResNet-50 benchmarks of a closely related study are reproduced as a validated reference. Audio-MAE is the stronger objective and the only configuration pretrained solely on the ADSiM data to surpass its supervised baseline on both metrics. The previously reported contrastive fine-tuning advantage is not reproduced under this protocol. External transfer sources provide a large and consistent benefit, with the source modality largely irrelevant at the available number of runs, while continued in-domain pretraining adds at best a small benefit. The strongest transformer configuration reaches the highest macro-F1 in the study, yet no self-supervised or transfer-based configuration surpasses the supervised ResNet-50 baseline on mAP, which is consistent with the limited scale of the in-domain data.

Index Terms—Railway sound classification, Self-supervised learning, Transfer learning, Vision Transformer, Masked Autoencoder, Contrastive learning

I. INTRODUCTION

With the continuing expansion of railway infrastructure [1] and traffic volume [2], the relevance of railway noise pollution increases. Railway noise can adversely affect exposed populations and has been associated with annoyance, sleep disturbance, and other health-related effects [3]–[6]. While transportation noise is commonly assessed using energy-equivalent indicators that aggregate sound exposure over a longer observation period, these provide limited information about recurring high-level peaks caused by individual train pass-bys [7]. In France, regulatory discussions have raised interest in complementing conventional energy-based indicators with event-based indicators and railway-event counting [7]. This shift toward event-level analysis increases the need for automatic methods that can identify and characterise individual pass-bys [8]. This work focuses on the classification of segmented railway environmental sound recordings into

predefined acoustic classes as one component of such an event-based analysis pipeline. Rather than addressing continuous event segmentation in long-term recordings, it studies the representation-learning problem underlying downstream classification on labelled railway sound events.

II. RELATED WORK

Recent studies show that audio classification models can be adapted to railway sound classification and event-based noise analysis. Betton-Ployon et al. [9] use YAMNet, a CNN-based audio classifier pretrained on AudioSet, to detect vehicle-like events in long-term railway noise recordings. Since YAMNet provides only broad classes such as “Vehicle”, the authors combine it with signal-processing criteria and a Railway Trained Classifier (RTC), obtained by freezing YAMNet’s convolutional filters and adapting the final dense layers to a custom labelled event database via transfer learning. This reduces false positives, but the method remains limited in urban environments, where road traffic and railway noise are difficult to separate. Schachinger *et al.* [10] investigate self-supervised learning (SSL) for railway sound classification, comparing a Masked Autoencoder (MAE) objective with a contrastive triplet learning (CTL) objective, both using a ResNet-50 encoder followed by supervised fine-tuning. On a weakly labelled and highly imbalanced dataset, CTL improves the macro-averaged F1-score (macro-F1) from 0.916 to 0.941, whereas MAE falls below their supervised baseline at 0.897. External transfer learning from pretrained audio or vision models is not investigated.

While these studies demonstrate the feasibility of deep learning for railway sound classification, their methods are mainly based on CNN architectures, whereas the broader audio classification field has increasingly shifted toward transformer encoders and large-scale pretraining. The Audio Spectrogram Transformer (AST) [11] introduced a convolution-free architecture for audio classification by transferring the patch-based Vision Transformer (ViT) design [12] to log-Mel spectrograms, processing two-dimensional patches with a DeiT-based transformer encoder [13]. AST outperformed previous convolution-based models on several benchmarks, including AudioSet, establishing a transformer-based reference model for audio classification.

Audio-MAE [14] adapts the MAE framework from computer vision [15] to audio spectrograms by masking a high

fraction of spectrogram patches during SSL pretraining, processing only the visible patches with a ViT encoder while a lightweight decoder reconstructs the missing regions. After pretraining, the encoder is fine-tuned on downstream tasks, demonstrating that masked spectrogram reconstruction can learn transferable audio representations from unlabeled data. AST and Audio-MAE represent two important reference models for modern audio classification, covering supervised transformer adaptation from vision to audio and spectrogram-based SSL pretraining followed by fine-tuning, respectively. Later models further support this trend toward transformer-based pretrained audio encoders [16], [17], yet to the author’s knowledge, these methods have not been systematically evaluated for railway environmental sound classification.

Transfer learning is central to this gap, as transformer models typically require large-scale pretraining to perform well on limited downstream data, a pattern established by ViT in computer vision [12]. In audio classification, AudioSet provides such a large-scale source dataset for audio event recognition [18]. In this work, transfer into the target audio task is characterised along two axes: a modality axis, distinguishing same-modality (e.g., AudioSet) from cross-modality sources (e.g., ImageNet [11], [19]) and a distribution axis, distinguishing in-distribution from out-of-distribution sources. Both axes build on standard transfer-learning and domain-shift concepts [20], [21]. Their combination into a single two-axis scheme is used here as an organising device. Additionally, a transfer source may serve either as a direct fine-tuning initialization or as a starting point for continued pretraining on the target dataset. This terminology is used throughout the work.

Large-scale supervised or self-supervised pretraining can provide strong downstream audio representations [11], [14], [16], [17], [22], which is particularly relevant for railway sound classification, where existing studies report substantial data limitations such as difficulty separating railway and road traffic noise [9], weak labels, class imbalance, and heterogeneous recording durations [10].

III. AIM AND CONTRIBUTIONS

The preceding review shows that transformer-based spectrogram encoders have not yet been systematically evaluated for railway sound classification, and the role of different transfer-learning strategies in this domain remains insufficiently understood. This work addresses this gap by evaluating transformer-based SSL and transfer learning on the same ADSiM dataset as [10], which combines a large unlabeled railway audio set with a smaller labeled subset, making it well suited for evaluating learning approaches under typical data constraints such as limited label availability, class imbalance, and variable recording durations.

The contributions of this work are threefold:

- It establishes validated reference results for the ADSiM classification task by reproducing the ResNet-50 supervised and CTL self-supervised benchmarks of [10].

- It adapts transformer-based spectrogram encoders to railway sound classification by evaluating Audio-MAE and extending the CTL framework of [10] to a ViT-Base architecture.
- It systematically analyzes transfer-learning strategies along both the modality and distribution axes.

Based on these contributions and to provide a systematic first evaluation of transformer-based SSL and transfer learning for railway environmental sound classification, this work addresses three research questions:

- **RQ1.** How does Audio-MAE pretraining compare with CTL pretraining for a ViT-Base encoder on the ADSiM railway environmental sound classification task?
- **RQ2.** How do different transfer-learning strategies affect downstream classification performance on ADSiM?
- **RQ3.** How does a ViT-Base encoder perform across the investigated self-supervised and transfer-learning settings compared with the ResNet-50 reference configurations (the supervised-from-scratch baseline $R-B$ and the CTL reference $R-C$)?

IV. METHOD

This chapter describes the methodology used to address the research questions. The experimental workflow proceeds in three stages: (i) reproduction of [10] as a validated reference; (ii) self-supervised pretraining on the ADSiM unlabeled dataset using MAE and CTL; and (iii) supervised training on the ADSiM labeled dataset, either from scratch or via fine-tuning of a pretrained encoder. Figure 1 visualizes the experimental setup. Transfer learning along both axes: modality and distribution, is realized by initializing the encoder with different weights: AudioSet and ImageNet as publicly available sources, and ADSiM weights trained in this work, either from random initialization or as continued pretraining. To isolate the effects of SSL and transfer learning, supervised baselines are trained from scratch with random initialization. Table I summarizes the resulting set of evaluated encoder configurations¹.

A. Audio-MAE

The Audio-MAE framework learns spectrogram representations by reconstructing masked patches (Figure 2). The input spectrogram is split into non-overlapping patches, of which a high fraction is masked. Only the visible patches are processed by the encoder $f(\cdot)$, and the decoder $g(\cdot)$ reconstructs the masked regions $r(\cdot)$ from the encoded visible patches and masked positions. The training objective is the MSE between the reconstructed patches $r(\cdot)$ and the corresponding targets $t(\cdot)$ [14].

Fixed two-dimensional sinusoidal-cosine positional embeddings are used, consistent with the default Audio-MAE configuration [14], and are regenerated analytically for the specific patch grid to ensure correct positional alignment independent

¹Publicly available on GitHub: <https://github.com/IvanBirkmaier/train-passby-transformers>

Fig. 1: General experimental setup comprising self-supervised training (left), supervised training (right), and transfer learning as a shared component (top).

Type	Configuration	Encoder	Pretraining Method	Encoder Weights
Baselines (from scratch)	R-B	ResNet-50	–	Random
	V-B	ViT-Base	–	Random
Pretrained Encoders	R-C	ResNet-50	CTL	ADSiM
	V-C	ViT-Base	CTL	ADSiM
	V-M	ViT-Base	MAE	ADSiM
	V-M-AS*	ViT-Base	MAE	AudioSet
	V-IM*	ViT-Base	Supervised	ImageNet
Adapted Encoders	V-M-AS	ViT-Base	MAE	AudioSet → ADSiM
	V-M-IM	ViT-Base	MAE	ImageNet → ADSiM
	V-C-IM	ViT-Base	CTL	ImageNet → ADSiM

TABLE I: Summary of all training configurations. Entries marked with an asterisk (*) use only published weights without further pretraining on ADSiM. The arrow notation (\rightarrow) denotes continued pretraining from public weights (left) on the target domain (right).

Fig. 2: Masked Autoencoder pretraining. The encoder $f(\cdot)$ processes visible spectrogram patches, and the decoder $g(\cdot)$ reconstructs the masked patches $r(\cdot)$ by minimizing $MSE(r(\cdot), t(\cdot))$. Figure modified from [14].

of the initialization source. When loading ViT AudioSet or ImageNet checkpoints, the original positional embeddings are discarded and replaced by newly computed sinusoidal embeddings matching the target patch grid, rather than interpolated. For ImageNet initialization, the three-channel RGB patch-embedding weights are converted to single-channel by averaging across the channel dimension (Equation 1), following AST [11]. All remaining encoder parameters are transferred

directly where tensor shapes match.

$$W_{1\text{ch}} = \text{mean}(W_{3\text{ch}}, \text{dim} = 1). \quad (1)$$

Appendix D provides a detailed overview of the hyperparameter settings.

B. Contrastive Triplet Learning

The CTL model follows [10], with corrections to checkpoint selection described in Section IV-C. Figure 3 illustrates the procedure. Each training sample forms a triplet of anchor $a(\cdot)$, positive $p(\cdot)$, and negative $n(\cdot)$, where the positive is derived from the same recording as the anchor and both undergo independent stochastic augmentations. The negative is sampled uniformly from the remaining unlabeled files using a deterministic seed $s = i + e \cdot N$, ensuring a different but reproducible negative per epoch. The encoder $f(\cdot)$ maps each view into a representation, which an multilayer perceptron (MLP) projection head $h(\cdot)$ projects to a 128-dimensional embedding space. The objective minimizes anchor–negative similarity and maximizes anchor–positive similarity. Hyperparameter settings are detailed in Appendix D.

Fig. 3: Contrastive triplet learning. The encoder $f(\cdot)$ and projection head $h(\cdot)$ map anchor $a(\cdot)$, positive $p(\cdot)$, and negative $n(\cdot)$ into an embedding space where anchor–positive similarity is maximized and anchor–negative similarity is minimized. Figure modified from [23].

The model uses a temperature-scaled triplet loss with $\tau = 0.07$ and margin $m = 0.5$, identical to [10]:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{triplet}} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \max \left(m - \frac{\text{sim}(\mathbf{a}_i, \mathbf{p}_i)}{\tau} + \frac{\text{sim}(\mathbf{a}_i, \mathbf{n}_i)}{\tau}, 0 \right), \quad (2)$$

where $\text{sim}(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}) = \frac{\mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{v}}{\|\mathbf{u}\| \|\mathbf{v}\|}$ denotes cosine similarity. Following [24], the downstream representation is taken directly from the encoder output, before the projection head. The projection head uses ReLU for ResNet-50 [10] and GELU for ViT [12]. When ImageNet weights are loaded for the ViT encoder, the patch-embedding adaptation from Section IV-A is applied.

C. Validation Loss Collapse

During reproduction of [10], a mathematical issue was identified in the CTL validation loss: stochastic augmentations were omitted in the validation path, causing anchor–positive cosine similarity to approach 1 and the validation loss to collapse toward a degenerate floor (Figure 9), independent of representational quality. Checkpoint selection based on the degenerate signal is therefore unreliable and cannot distinguish a well-trained encoder from a poorly-trained one.

This is consistent with contrastive learning methods such as SimCLR [24] and MoCo [25], which define positive pairs through independent stochastic augmentations. A validation positive bypassing these augmentations pushes the loss into a near-degenerate regime, analogous to easily satisfied triplets that provide no meaningful learning signal [26], [27], though here caused by the absence of augmentation rather than the mining strategy. A formal degeneracy analysis is provided in Appendix C. To separate reproduction from methodological improvement, two tracks are distinguished: the first reproduces [10] including the validation loss collapse, while the second applies the corrected CTL pipeline described in Section IV-B with consistent augmentations and training-loss-based checkpoint selection. Hyperparameter settings for the reproduction are detailed in Appendix D-A.

V. SUPERVISED TRAINING

Analogously to Section IV-C, a second methodological issue was identified during reproduction: multi-metric early stopping. Monitoring multiple correlated metrics in parallel increases the probability of selecting outlier checkpoints driven

Fig. 4: Spectrogram tensor orientations. (Left) BCFT (Batch \times Channel \times Frequency \times Time): frequency as height, time as width. (Right) BCTF: time as height, frequency as width. Augmentation masks are applied along their respective axes in both cases.

by validation-set sampling noise [28]. This concern is particularly acute in the setting of [10], where macro-F1 estimates exhibit high variance due to the strong influence of the small *Curve Squeal* class, as discussed in Section VI-B.

These considerations, together with the supervised-training hyperparameters selected in [10], motivate not reusing the original recipe (recipe S) as the default optimization setting for the ResNet-50 baseline experiments in this work. Instead, recipe S is retained unchanged only for the reproduction of [10], while two independent recipes are defined for the remaining experiments: recipe B for baseline models trained from random initialization and recipe F for fine-tuning pretrained encoders. This separation reflects a deliberate methodological choice: training from scratch and fine-tuning a pretrained encoder pose fundamentally different optimization problems and therefore warrant distinct hyperparameter selections. All remaining components: audio frontend, loss function, early stopping, seeding protocol, and classification-head architecture are held constant across both settings. A direct performance comparison between recipe S and recipe F is provided in the recipe comparison in Section VI-H, and the full hyperparameters for all recipes are documented in Appendix E.

A. Audio Frontend

A unified audio frontend is applied across all encoders and training phases to eliminate the input representation as a confounding variable. All audio is resampled to 32 kHz and converted to log-Mel spectrograms with 128 Mel bins, FFT size 2048, and hop length 512, using BCTF (Batch \times Channel \times Time \times Frequency) tensor orientation (Figure 4) consistent with Audio-MAE [14]. Details of the audio frontend and augmentation pipeline are provided in Appendix G as well as Appendix D. For the reproduction of [10], the original augmentation configuration is retained.

Location	# Files (%)	Sample Rate (kHz)	Duration (h)
Curve 1	34107 (71.8)	50/32/48 [†]	84.2
Curve 2	8087 (17.0)	32	29.5
Straight 1	2735 (5.8)	51.2	10.8
Curve 3	1332 (2.8)	32	6.5
Curve 4	1258 (2.6)	32	6.5
Total	47519 (100)	—	137.5

TABLE II: Composition of the unlabeled ADSiM dataset by recording location. [†]Curve 1 contains three original sample rates: 50 kHz (97.1%), 32 kHz (2.3%), 48 kHz (0.7%).

VI. EXPERIMENTS AND RESULTS

This chapter reports the experimental setup and results. Section VI-A describes the dataset, Section VI-B specifies test splits, and the evaluation protocol. The remaining sections present the experimental results along the two transfer-learning axes defined in Chapter I. Section VI-E evaluates same-modality, domain-transfer SSL pretraining on the target dataset as a direct initialisation (RQ1, RQ3); Section VI-F isolates the modality axis by comparing same- and cross-modality external sources as direct initialisations (RQ2); and Section VI-G addresses the distribution axis by evaluating continued pretraining of externally initialised encoders on ADSiM (RQ2).

A. Dataset

The ADSiM dataset is an ongoing collection recorded as part of wayside monitoring on the Austrian rail network. The ADSiM research project aims to automate the detection of acoustic anomalies such as curve squeal and braking noise, as well as non-railway background sounds and faulty sensor signals, in continuous railway noise monitoring using AI-based classifiers.² Microphones were placed across five measurement locations recording individual train pass-bys: four at curves (*Curve 1–4*) and one at a straight track section (*Straight 1*), with varying measurement conditions and sample rates (Table II). This work uses the same version of the collection as [10].

a) Unlabeled Dataset: The unlabeled dataset used in this work comprises $n = 47519$ recordings (137.5 h) distributed across all five measurement locations (Table II). The distribution is strongly imbalanced: *Curve 1* alone accounts for 71.8% of all files.

b) Labeled Dataset: The labeled dataset comprises $n = 4720$ recordings across four classes (Figure 5) and three locations (Table III).

The dataset exhibits a pronounced class imbalance: *Screeching* accounts for 46.6% of samples, while the minority class *Curve Squeal* ($n = 142$) contributes only 3.0%. The class composition also varies across locations, with 89.4% of *Curve Squeal* samples originating from *Curve 2*.

²See the ADSiM project page (accessed May 29, 2026).

Class	Curve 3	Curve 2	Curve 4	Total
Screeching	437	1187	576	2200
Negative	336	845	484	1665
Curve Squeal	7	127	8	142
Both [Screeching, Curve Squeal]	166	474	73	713
Total	946	2633	1141	4720

TABLE III: Class and location distribution of the ADSiM labeled dataset.

Fig. 5: Visualization of the four classes using representative spectrograms. (a) *Screeching* is characterized by multiple narrow high-frequency peaks. (b) *Curve Squeal* typically shows one or a few dominant tonal components. (c) *Both* combines characteristics of *Screeching* and *Curve Squeal*. (d) *Negative* contains no clearly identifiable target signal. The shown negative example is one of the clearer samples. Many negative samples are less distinct.

c) Acoustic Characterisation: To assess how differing recording conditions translate into measurable acoustic differences, a 2D PCA was computed on eight scale-invariant spectral and temporal features (Appendix B). Figure 6 projects the resulting feature space along four overlays: recording location, track geometry, duration, and loudness proxy (RMS level in dB). The first two principal components explain 75.6% of the feature variance.

Three observations are central. First, panels (a) and (b) show that the curve locations overlap substantially, while *Straight 1* forms a clearly separated cluster, indicating that the curve–straight contrast is the dominant structural axis in acoustic feature space. Second, panel (c) reveals a pronounced duration

PCA of acoustic features with four post-hoc overlays

Same PCA fit on 8 acoustic features ($n = 7090$ points, max 1500 per location). Overlays are explanatory variables, not inputs to the PCA.

Fig. 6: Two-dimensional PCA of eight scale-invariant acoustic features with four explanatory overlays: (a) recording location with centroids and 1.5σ ellipses, (b) track geometry (curves vs. straight), (c) recording duration in seconds, and (d) RMS level in dB as loudness proxy. A balanced sample of up to 1500 files per location was drawn ($n = 7090$). PC1 and PC2 account for 44.3% and 31.3% of the variance, respectively.

gradient along PC1. Third, panel (d) shows that the loudness proxy spans roughly 30 dB and aligns most strongly with PC2, with louder recordings overlapping the *Straight 1* region. Recording duration and loudness are therefore not independent nuisance variables but explanatory factors that jointly account for a substantial portion of the variance captured by PC1 and PC2.

These observations imply that the SSL-pretraining \rightarrow fine-tuning pipeline constitutes a domain-transfer scenario rather than a same-domain data-augmentation scenario, since the pretraining distribution is structurally broader than, and partially disjoint from, the downstream target distribution. The downstream task draws exclusively from *Curve 2–4* (Table III), while the pretraining dataset additionally contains *Curve 1* (71.8%) and the acoustically distinct *Straight 1* (5.8%).

However, since the four curve locations overlap strongly in acoustic feature space despite differing measurement conditions, transfer should remain feasible, with *Straight 1* serving as a supporting source of variability rather than a dominant distractor. The duration and loudness gradients additionally motivate the input-length and normalisation choices discussed in Appendix G.

B. Experimental Design

All experiments use 10 independent runs per configuration per test split (20 runs total), each with a distinct seed from a fixed set, and a deterministic CUDA backend, inspired by [29]. Seeds control model initialisation (random weights), dataloader shuffling, augmentation state, and dropout masks, while train/validation/test partitions remain constant. For the

Fig. 7: Joint class \times location distribution of the test set for ADSIM_S, ADSIM_N, and the full-dataset. (Left) all four classes with stacked location contributions; the right y -axis (grey) scales the labeled-dataset bars. (Right) zoomed view of *Curve Squeal*, the rarest class ($n = 14$ in both test splits vs. $n = 142$ in the full dataset). Both ADSIM_S and ADSIM_N preserve nearly identical class sizes, but ADSIM_N was stratified jointly across class and location, yielding lower distributional deviation from the full-dataset (cf. Table IV). *Both** denotes samples carrying dual labels (*Screeching* and *Curve Squeal*).

reproduction of [10], the original protocol is retained: seed 96 fixes only the train/validation/test partition, while model initialisation, data loading, augmentation, and the cuDNN backend are left unseeded and non-deterministic. Repeated runs therefore differ despite the fixed data split.

a) Test Splits: A Monte-Carlo simulation of the test split from [10] (ADSIM_S) shows that approximately 66% of the run-to-run macro-F1 variance is attributable to the smallest class (*Curve Squeal*, $n = 14$; see Appendix A and Figure 8). A single split under these conditions does not reliably separate genuine model quality from split-specific sampling variance. To address this, an independent test split ADSIM_N was defined, stratified across both class labels and locations simultaneously. As shown in Table IV and Figure 7, ADSIM_N achieves substantially lower distributional deviations from the full-dataset (0.80%/0.82%) than ADSIM_S (3.00%/3.06%).

b) Test Metrics: macro-F1 is used as the primary metric for comparability with prior work, despite its high sensitivity to the smallest class composition (Figure 8). As a secondary metric, mean average precision (mAP) is introduced, computed from the same checkpoint and providing an audio-tagging perspective on model performance [18], [30]. This dual-metric view is motivated by the observation that detecting acoustic phenomena in the ADSiM railway recordings is operationally closer to audio event tagging than to single-label classification. mAP is computed one-versus-rest over all four classes and macro-averaged, with the *Negative* class included to penalise false-positive detections.

c) Reporting Convention: For each configuration, the median across all runs is reported as the point estimate for

Fig. 8: Monte Carlo simulation (10 000 runs, true accuracy = 0.90). (Left) median macro-F1 with $\pm\sigma$ error bars for each split configuration; ADSIM_S and ADSIM_N yield nearly identical distributions ($\sigma \approx 0.023$), while the class-balanced ADSIM_F condition (Appendix A) exhibits roughly half the standard deviation ($\sigma = 0.014$). (Right) per-class contribution to the total macro-F1 variance; *Curve Squeal* ($n = 14$) alone accounts for approximately 66% of the variance in the imbalanced splits, whereas ADSIM_F distributes variance equally (25% per class). *Both** denotes samples carrying dual labels (*Screeching* and *Curve Squeal*).

both metrics.

d) Statistical Testing: Two procedures are applied. Pair-wise comparisons use Student’s t -test [31] at $\alpha = 0.05$ with Bonferroni correction [32] per experiment block, and Cohen’s d [33] to quantify effect sizes. One-way ANOVA [34] with Tukey Honestly Significant Difference (Tukey HSD) [35] post-hoc test is used to assess whether performance differs significantly between ADSIM_S and ADSIM_N.

C. Reference Reproduction

a) Pretraining learning curve: The pretraining-loss curves are shown in Figure 9. Training loss decreases monotonically, while validation loss collapses toward a degenerate floor, consistent with the degeneracy analysis in Appendix C and the loss curve reported by [10], [23]. This collapse, together with the non-deterministic sampling procedure used to construct the original validation set, precluded an exact reproduction of the pretraining run. Therefore multiple runs were conducted and the checkpoint whose loss curve most closely matched the original was selected. The resulting checkpoint lies at epoch 77.

b) Downstream results: Table V reports the per-split and cross-split medians, effect sizes, and p -values. Figure 10 visualises the run-to-run distributions.

None of the three comparisons reaches significance (Table V). The per-split effect sizes are oppositely signed, medium favouring Finetuning on ADSIM_S ($d = +0.61$) and small-to-medium favouring Baseline on ADSIM_N ($d = -0.45$), and cancel in the cross-split comparison ($d = +0.10$).

c) Run-to-run variance vs. Monte-Carlo prediction: The Monte-Carlo simulation of Appendix A and Figure 8

Split	Set	Mean Abs. Dev.	Std. Dev.	Max Abs. Dev.
ADSIM_S	Validation	3.00%	4.58%	10.87%
	Testing	3.06%	3.64%	8.15%
ADSIM_N	Validation	0.80%	1.35%	3.72%
	Testing	0.82%	1.36%	3.72%

TABLE IV: Distributional deviation from the full-dataset joint class \times location distribution for ADSIM_S and ADSIM_N, reported separately for validation and test sets.

	ADSIM_S	ADSIM_N	Cross-split
Baseline (median macro-F1, %)	91.5	89.7	90.9
Finetuning (median macro-F1, %)	93.1	89.2	90.6
Cohen’s d	+0.61	-0.45	+0.10
p (Student)	0.059	0.167	0.665

TABLE V: Reproduction results. Student’s t -test, Bonferroni-corrected ($\alpha_{\text{Bonf}} = 0.0167$). *Baseline* denotes the supervised ResNet-50 trained from scratch and *Finetuning* the CTL-pretrained ResNet-50, both under Recipe S. $n = 20$ unseeded runs per condition per split ($n = 40$ cross-split).

Fig. 9: Triplet-loss learning curves during contrastive pretraining (log scale). (Left) Reproduced run; the horizontal line marks the checkpoint selected by validation loss (epoch 77). (Right) Original curve (selected checkpoint 17, i.e. epoch ≈ 85) reported by [10], [23]. Both without stochastic augmentations on the validation path, $\text{sim}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{p}) \rightarrow 1$ and the loss converges toward the degenerate regime.

Fig. 10: Test macro-F1 by split and initialisation method. Brackets indicate Student’s t -test results (Bonferroni-corrected); n.s. = not significant. Gold diamonds mark the values reported by [10], [23].

Fig. 11: (left) Audio-MAE pretraining loss for the ViT-Base encoder, initialisation comparison. (right) Contrastive triplet pretraining loss for the ViT-Base encoder, initialisation comparison.

predicts macro-F1 standard deviations of 2.27% (ADSIM_S) and 2.29% (ADSIM_N). Observed per-split standard deviations range from 1.44% to 1.84%, systematically below the simulated upper bound but of the same order of magnitude. The gap is partly explained by the simulation’s fixed accuracy assumption of 0.90, whereas empirical accuracies cluster slightly higher (≈ 0.91), which mechanically reduces variance and is further investigated in Section VI-I.

D. Pretraining Convergence

Each pretraining configuration (Table I) was trained until downstream improvements plateaued. Figures 11 and 12 show the corresponding loss curves.

All Audio-MAE configurations converge smoothly within their epoch budget. AudioSet initialisation (V-M-AS) initially reaches a lower reconstruction loss in fewer epochs than random initialisation (V-M), but plateaus early and is eventually surpassed by the random-initialisation run. ImageNet initialisation (V-M-IM) does not improve upon the random-initialisation loss. For contrastive pretraining, ImageNet initialisation (V-C-IM) converges faster and to a lower loss than V-C. The ResNet-50 contrastive run (Figure 12) behaves similarly to its ViT-Base counterpart.

ADSiM Pretraining (ResNet-50 Encoder): Loss per Epoch

Fig. 12: Contrastive triplet pretraining loss for the ResNet-50 encoder.

E. SSL Downstream performance

This experiment quantifies the effect of same-modality, domain-transfer self-supervised pretraining on ADSiM as a direct initialisation source (see Section VI-A). Each pretrained configuration (R-C, V-M, V-C; $n = 20$) is compared against its baseline (R-B, V-B; $n = 20$) using the protocol from Section VI-B. Best checkpoints were selected by cross-split median over the available pretraining-epoch grid. Because this selection uses the same cross-split metric that is subsequently reported, the resulting per-configuration medians are optimistic and the associated p -values are anti-conservative; the consequences are discussed in Section VIII-C. Figures 13 and 14 show cross-split macro-F1 and mAP (median with interquartile range (IQR)) across this grid for all SSL configurations.

Several patterns emerge. R-C shows a monotonic decrease in downstream macro-F1 with increasing pretraining duration. V-M continues to improve up to the maximum tested epoch with diminishing gains, while V-C plateaus at epoch 150. The continued-pretraining configurations (Section VI-G) are included for completeness: V-C-IM and V-M-IM are largely unaffected by pretraining duration, whereas V-M-AS peaks at epoch 30 and declines thereafter.

a) *Test results:* Table VI reports the three baseline-vs.-fine-tuning comparisons. Three tests per metric, Bonferroni-corrected with $\alpha_{\text{Bonf}} = 0.0167$. V-M significantly outperforms V-B on both metrics (+4.0 pp macro-F1, $d = +1.02$; +1.7 pp mAP, $d = +2.13$). R-C significantly underperforms R-B on both metrics (-4.9 pp macro-F1, $d = -2.36$; -2.5 pp mAP, $d = -2.97$). V-C vs. V-B does not reach the corrected threshold on either metric (+1.2 pp macro-F1, $p = 0.805$; +0.4 pp mAP, $p = 0.104$).

F. External Transfer Sources

This experiment isolates the modality axis: external pretrained weights used as a *direct* initialisation, without any subsequent self-supervised pretraining on ADSiM. Two out-of-distribution sources are compared against the random-initialisation baseline (V-B): a same-modality source (Au-

Fig. 13: Cross-split macro-F1 (median with IQR) as a function of pretraining epoch for all six SSL configurations. Dashed lines indicate the respective reference: the supervised baseline for direct-pretraining configurations (e.g. R-B, V-B) and the transfer-initialised counterpart for continued-pretraining configurations.

Fig. 14: Cross-split mAP (median with IQR) as a function of pretraining epoch for all six SSL configurations. Dashed lines indicate the respective reference: the supervised baseline for direct-pretraining configurations (e.g. R-B, V-B) and the transfer-initialised counterpart for continued-pretraining configurations.

dioSet MAE, V-M-AS*) and a cross-modality source (ImageNet supervised, V-IM*). The two sources are additionally compared directly against each other. $n = 20$ per condition; three tests per metric, Bonferroni-corrected with $\alpha_{\text{Bonf}} = 0.0167$.

Both transfer sources significantly outperform the random-initialisation baseline on both metrics (V-M-AS*: +4.4 pp macro-F1 / +2.4 pp mAP; V-IM*: +4.1 pp macro-F1 / +2.3 pp mAP). The direct comparison between the two sources does not reach significance on either metric (macro-F1: $d = +0.13$, $p = 0.676$; mAP: $d = +0.45$, $p = 0.159$).

G. Continued Pretraining

This experiment evaluates the distribution axis: whether continued self-supervised pretraining of an externally ini-

Comparison @ ep.	Metric	Baseline (%)	Finetuning (%)	Δ (pp)	Cohen’s d	p
R-B vs. R-C @ 10	macro-F1	86.9	82.0	-4.9	-2.36	< 0.001 (↓)
	mAP	97.6	95.1	-2.5	-2.97	< 0.001 (↓)
V-B vs. V-M @ 120	macro-F1	80.4	84.4	+4.0	+1.02	0.003 (↑)
	mAP	94.2	95.9	+1.7	+2.13	< 0.001 (↑)
V-B vs. V-C @ 150	macro-F1	80.4	81.6	+1.2	+0.08	0.805 (n.s.)
	mAP	94.2	94.6	+0.4	+0.53	0.104 (n.s.)

TABLE VI: Effect of ADSiM self-supervised pretraining as direct initialisation (best-checkpoint comparison, cross-split, $n = 20$ per condition). Bonferroni-corrected $\alpha_{\text{Bonf}} = 0.0167$. \uparrow = significant gain; \downarrow = significant loss; n.s. = not significant.

Comparison	Metric	Baseline (%)	Finetuning (%)	Δ (pp)	Cohen’s d	p
V-B vs. V-M-AS*	macro-F1	80.4	84.8	+4.4	+1.39	< 0.001 (↑)
	mAP	94.2	96.6	+2.4	+2.91	< 0.001 (↑)
V-B vs. V-IM*	macro-F1	80.4	84.5	+4.1	+1.12	0.001 (↑)
	mAP	94.2	96.5	+2.3	+2.62	< 0.001 (↑)
V-IM* vs. V-M-AS*	macro-F1	84.5	84.8	+0.3	+0.13	0.676 (n.s.)
	mAP	96.5	96.6	+0.1	+0.45	0.159 (n.s.)

TABLE VII: External transfer-only (direct) initialisation, ViT-Base. The first two comparisons reference the random-initialisation baseline (V-B); the third compares the two external sources directly. Bonferroni-corrected $\alpha_{\text{Bonf}} = 0.0167$. \uparrow = significant gain; n.s. = not significant.

tialised encoder on the ADSiM dataset (transfer \rightarrow ADSiM) adds performance over its reference condition. Two reference conditions are distinguished, yielding two groups. *Group 1* references each continued-pretraining configuration against the corresponding ADSiM-only model (V-M, V-C), isolating the value of the external source as a starting point. *Group 2* references each continued-pretraining configuration against the corresponding external transfer-only initialisation (Figures 14,13; V-M-AS*, V-IM*), isolating the value of the appended ADSiM pretraining step itself. Each group comprises three tests per metric, Bonferroni-corrected with $\alpha_{\text{Bonf}} = 0.0167$. To remain consistent with the best-checkpoint protocol of Section VI-E each comparison uses the best cross-split checkpoint per configuration.

a) Group 1 (vs. ADSiM-only fine-tuning): No Group 1 comparison reaches significance on macro-F1. On mAP, V-M-AS significantly outperforms V-M ($d = +0.81$) and V-C-IM significantly outperforms V-C ($d = +1.29$). The V-M-IM vs. V-M comparison shows a point-estimate degradation on both metrics, but neither direction survives the corrected threshold ($p = 0.146$ macro-F1, $p = 0.047$ mAP). The macro-F1 point estimates are directionally consistent with the mAP signal: V-M-AS and V-C-IM above their ADSiM-only counterparts, V-M-IM below. The degradation of V-M-IM relative to V-M is consistent with its training dynamics: under the shared Recipe F, the ImageNet-initialised continued-pretraining models show the widest train-validation gap of all ViT configurations (Section VII), the standard signature of overfitting on the small labelled set. This indicates that the Recipe F learning-rate schedule is not well matched to strong initialisations on this dataset, a point developed as future work in Section VIII-D.

b) Group 2 (vs. external transfer-only): No Group 2 comparison reaches significance on macro-F1. On mAP, both

ImageNet-referenced comparisons show a significant degradation when the ADSiM step is appended (V-M-IM: $d = -1.15$; V-C-IM: $d = -1.33$). The AudioSet-referenced comparison (V-M-AS* vs. V-M-AS) does not reach significance on either metric ($p = 0.840$ macro-F1, $p = 0.413$ mAP). The large macro-F1 point-estimate gain (+2.5 pp) coexists with a near-zero Cohen’s d (+0.06) because the run distribution is right-skewed: the median macro-F1 of the continued model (87.3%) lies well above its mean (85.6%), whereas the two condition means are almost identical (85.4% vs 85.6%). Since Δ is reported as a difference of medians while Cohen’s d and the t -test operate on means, the two measures diverge for this comparison, and the t -test is the decisive statistic.

H. Recipe Comparison

This experiment is motivated by the revised supervised-training recipe used for the ResNet-50 baseline in this work (Section V) and by the large performance gap between recipe S in the reproduction setting (Section VI-C) and recipe F in the SSL-on-target setting (Section VI-E). To isolate the recipe effect, the two encoder families in this work (ResNet-50 and ViT-Base) are crossed with both downstream recipes. The transfer of Recipe S is approximate: differing tensor orientations between pretraining regimes prevent a one-to-one adoption. Optimiser, scheduler, learning rate, loss, and early-stopping configuration were retained from Recipe S. For ViT-Base, validation augmentation was replaced by uniform-length validation (required by positional-embedding interpolation) and tensor orientation was adapted; for ResNet-50, only tensor orientation was changed. As a consequence, the Recipe S condition is not an identical intervention across the two encoder families, which is relevant for interpreting the encoder-dependent pattern reported below. A complementary

Comparison @ ep.	Metric	ADSiM-only (%)	Continued (%)	Δ (pp)	Cohen’s d	p
V-M @ 120 vs. V-M-AS @ 30	macro-F1	84.4	87.3	+2.9	+0.51	0.116 (n.s.)
	mAP	95.9	96.4	+0.5	+0.81	0.015 (\uparrow)
V-M @ 120 vs. V-M-IM @ 5	macro-F1	84.4	83.4	-1.0	-0.47	0.146 (n.s.)
	mAP	95.9	95.2	-0.7	-0.65	0.047 (n.s.)
V-C @ 150 vs. V-C-IM @ 80	macro-F1	81.6	83.5	+1.9	+0.59	0.068 (n.s.)
	mAP	94.6	95.6	+1.0	+1.29	< 0.001 (\uparrow)

TABLE VIII: Continued pretraining vs. ADSiM-only fine-tuning (random-init SSL on target), best-checkpoint per configuration. Bonferroni-corrected $\alpha_{\text{Bonf}} = 0.0167$.

Comparison @ ep.	Metric	Transfer-only (%)	Continued (%)	Δ (pp)	Cohen’s d	p
V-M-AS* vs. V-M-AS (30)	macro-F1	84.8	87.3	+2.5	+0.06	0.840 (n.s.)
	mAP	96.6	96.4	-0.2	-0.26	0.413 (n.s.)
V-IM* vs. V-M-IM (5)	macro-F1	84.5	83.4	-1.1	-0.65	0.048 (n.s.)
	mAP	96.5	95.2	-1.3	-1.15	< 0.001 (\downarrow)
V-IM* vs. V-C-IM @ 80	macro-F1	84.5	83.5	-1.0	-0.50	0.120 (n.s.)
	mAP	96.5	95.6	-0.9	-1.33	< 0.001 (\downarrow)

TABLE IX: Continued pretraining vs. external transfer-only initialisation, best-checkpoint per configuration. Only $V-M-AS^* \rightarrow V-M-AS$ holds the SSL framework constant (MAE \rightarrow MAE); $V-IM^* \rightarrow V-M-IM$ and $V-IM^* \rightarrow V-C-IM$ change both the framework (supervised ImageNet init \rightarrow MAE / CTL) and add the ADSiM step. Bonferroni-corrected $\alpha_{\text{Bonf}} = 0.0167$.

Fig. 15: Cross-split macro-F1 (left) and mAP (right) (median with IQR) of R-C comparing downstream performance of Recipe S vs. Recipe F.

Fig. 16: Cross-split macro-F1 (left) and mAP (right) (median with IQR) of V-M-AS comparing downstream performance of Recipe S vs. Recipe F.

analysis on the reproduced ResNet-50 reference encoder of Section VI-C is reported in Appendix J.

Recipe S was applied to the same checkpoints selected under Recipe F in Section VI-E. Each comparison uses the best cross-split checkpoint as determined under Recipe F ($n = 20$ per condition), one per encoder family, at $\alpha = 0.05$ (single test per metric; no Bonferroni correction required). Because only one encoder per family is evaluated, the results below are exemplary per family rather than a family-level generalisation.

a) *Comparison 1: R-C encoder – Recipe F vs. Recipe S:* Figure 15 shows the recipe comparison across pretraining checkpoints; Table X reports the t -test results for the best-checkpoint comparison ($n = 20$ per condition).

b) *Comparison 2: V-M-AS encoder – Recipe F vs. Recipe S:* Figure 16 shows the recipe comparison across pretraining checkpoints; Table XI reports the t -test results for the best-checkpoint comparison ($n = 20$ per condition).

Both comparisons reach significance, but the direction of the recipe effect reverses across encoder families. For the ResNet-50 encoder R-C, Recipe S outperforms Recipe F (-7.2 pp

macro-F1, $d = -3.67$; -3.3 pp mAP, $d = -6.04$). For the ViT-Base encoder V-M-AS, Recipe F outperforms Recipe S ($+3.1$ pp macro-F1, $d = +0.76$; $+1.7$ pp mAP, $d = +2.21$). Since Recipes F and S differ on multiple axes (Appendix F-B) and the Recipe S transfer is not an identical intervention across encoder families, the reported effects reflect the recipe as a bundle.

I. Test-Split Dependency

All supervised training runs were jointly analysed using a one-way ANOVA with split (ADSiM_N vs. ADSiM_S) as the single factor, separately for macro-F1 and mAP. Tukey HSD is reported as a post-hoc test where the ANOVA reaches significance.

The split factor is highly significant for macro-F1 and explains 14.5% of the total variance; ADSiM_S is on average $+3.8\%$ higher than ADSiM_N. The 14.5% between-split variance and the $\approx 66\%$ small-class within-split variance (Appendix A) are complementary decompositions: the latter is the sampling-variance ceiling within a single split, the former

Metric	Recipe F (%)	Recipe S (%)	Δ (F-S, pp)	Cohen's d	p
macro-F1	82.0	89.2	-7.2	-3.67	< 0.001
mAP	95.1	98.4	-3.3	-6.04	< 0.001

TABLE X: R-C encoder, two downstream recipes, best-checkpoint, $\alpha = 0.05$. Δ and Cohen's d are both reported as Recipe F minus Recipe S.

Metric	Recipe F (%)	Recipe S (%)	Δ (F-S, pp)	Cohen's d	p
macro-F1	87.3	84.2	+3.1	+0.76	0.022
mAP	96.4	94.7	+1.7	+2.21	< 0.001

TABLE XI: V-M-AS encoder, two downstream recipes, best-checkpoint, $\alpha = 0.05$. Δ and Cohen's d are both reported as Recipe F minus Recipe S.

Metric	Mean ADSIM_N (%)	Mean ADSIM_S (%)	F	p	η^2	Tukey p
macro-F1	81.1	84.9	118.75	< 10^{-24}	0.145	< 0.001
mAP	95.1	94.5	3.51	0.062	0.005	—

TABLE XII: One-way ANOVA of all supervised training run samples.

Fig. 17: Per-class F1 distributions: Monte-Carlo simulation vs. real training runs, by split. *Both** denotes samples carrying dual labels (Screeching and Curve Squeal).

is the additional shift attributable to the choice between splits. The split factor is not significant for mAP at $\alpha = 0.05$.

a) *Per-class F1 distributions*: Figure 17 compares the per-class F1 distributions of the real training runs against the Monte-Carlo-simulated F1 distributions of Appendix A, separately for ADSIM_N, and ADSIM_S. The medians of the real-run distributions for the small class (*Curve Squeal*, $n = 14$) are systematically higher on ADSIM_S than on ADSIM_N. The medians of the larger classes are comparable across splits.

J. Best-configuration overview

Table XIII reports the cross-split median performance of the investigated configurations for both metrics after best-checkpoint selection (Section VI-E, Figures 13, 14). Figure 18 shows the corresponding run-level cross-split distributions for each configuration.

Fig. 18: Run-level cross-split distributions for the best-checkpoint per encoder/SSL configuration. Top: macro-F1. Bottom: mAP. Coloured points: split membership; black bar: median across both splits.

VII. TRAINING DYNAMICS

Beyond test-set performance, the training dynamics of the different configurations were examined. The analysis uses the validation macro-F1 (also used for early stopping); the training curves are reported as the average of the per-split medians across the two test splits, with the average IQR band.

Two distinct training behaviours were observed: (1) moderate convergence and (2) fast convergence with a subsequent

Configuration	Encoder	Pretrain Data	macro-F1 (%)	mAP (%)
<i>Baseline (supervised, from scratch)</i>				
R-B	ResNet-50	Random	86.9	97.6
V-B	ViT-Base	Random	80.4	94.2
<i>Supervised Pretraining</i>				
V-IM*	ViT-Base	ImageNet	84.5	96.5
<i>Contrastive Triplet Learning</i>				
R-C	ResNet-50	ADSiM	82.0	95.1
V-C	ViT-Base	ADSiM	81.6	94.6
V-C-IM	ViT-Base	ImageNet → ADSiM	83.5	95.6
<i>Masked Autoencoder</i>				
V-M	ViT-Base	ADSiM	84.4	95.9
V-M-AS*	ViT-Base	AudioSet	84.8	96.6
V-M-AS	ViT-Base	AudioSet → ADSiM	87.3	96.4
V-M-IM	ViT-Base	ImageNet → ADSiM	83.4	95.2

TABLE XIII: Best-checkpoint cross-split performance per configuration, grouped by pretraining method. Median over $n = 20$ runs per row. Within each group, the highest macro-F1 and mAP median are shown in bold.

Fig. 19: Validation macro-F1 convergence of the baseline configurations. Moderate convergence characterises almost all baseline configurations.

decline in validation macro-F1; these are further discussed in Chapter VIII.

VIII. DISCUSSION

This chapter discusses the experimental results presented in Chapter VI. Section VIII-A recapitulates and interprets the main findings in relation to the research questions. Section VIII-B relates the findings to the existing literature. Section VIII-C reflects on the limitations of the experimental design, and Section VIII-D discusses implications and outlines directions for future work.

A. Summary and Interpretation

Chapter I posed three research questions. The following paragraphs recapitulate the main findings per research question and per methodological theme, and interpret them in turn.

Fig. 20: Validation macro-F1 convergence of the ViT-Base contrastive triplet configurations. Fast convergence with a subsequent decline was observed primarily for the ImageNet-initialised continued-pretraining configurations (CL variant).

Fig. 21: Validation macro-F1 convergence of the ViT-Base MAE configurations. Fast convergence with a subsequent decline was observed primarily for the ImageNet-initialised continued-pretraining configurations.

a) *RQ1: Audio-MAE versus contrastive triplet learning on the target dataset:* Audio-MAE pretraining on the ADSiM dataset from random initialisation (V-M), evaluated in Section VI-E, significantly outperforms the supervised ViT-Base baseline on both metrics (+4.0 pp macro-F1, $d = +1.02$, $p = 0.003$; +1.7 pp mAP, $d = +2.13$). Contrastive triplet pretraining on the same setup (V-C) yields a small mAP improvement that does not survive Bonferroni correction (+0.4 pp, $d = +0.53$, $p = 0.104$) and no detectable macro-F1 effect (+1.2 pp, $p = 0.805$). For a ViT-Base encoder on this dataset, Audio-MAE is therefore the stronger self-supervised objective, and is the only same-modality, in-domain configuration that improves over its supervised baseline on both metrics. This directly addresses RQ1: the two objectives are not interchangeable on ADSiM, and the masked-reconstruction objective yields a downstream improvement that the contrastive objective does not.

b) *RQ2: Transfer-learning strategies along the modality and distribution axes:* The transfer-learning results separate into a direct-initialisation result on the modality axis and a continued-pretraining result on the distribution axis.

On the modality axis, both external sources used as direct initialisation provide a large and consistent benefit over the random-initialisation baseline (V-B). The same-modality AudioSet source (V-M-AS*) and the cross-modality ImageNet source (V-IM*) improve macro-F1 by +4.4 pp and +4.1 pp respectively, with $d > 1$ in both cases, and mAP by +2.4 pp and +2.3 pp. The direct comparison between the two sources does not reach significance on either metric (macro-F1: $d = +0.13$, $p = 0.676$; mAP: $d = +0.45$, $p = 0.159$). At the available run count the modality of the external source therefore matters little when the source is used as a direct initialisation. This near-equivalence is a property of the direct-initialisation comparison in Section VI-F. It should not be read as evidence of strict equivalence, since absence of significance at $n = 20$ is not evidence of absence (Section VIII-C).

On the distribution axis, continued self-supervised pretraining of an externally initialised encoder on ADSiM was evaluated against two references. Relative to ADSiM-only pretraining (Group 1), continued AudioSet→ADSiM Audio-MAE (V-M-AS) and continued ImageNet→ADSiM contrastive triplet (V-C-IM) significantly outperform their ADSiM-only counterparts on mAP ($d = +0.81$ and $d = +1.29$). On macro-F1 the same comparisons remain directionally consistent but do not reach the corrected threshold (V-M-AS: +2.9 pp, $d = +0.51$, $p = 0.116$; V-C-IM: +1.9 pp, $d = +0.59$, $p = 0.068$). Relative to the external transfer-only initialisation (Group 2), the appended ADSiM step behaves differently depending on the source. Starting from AudioSet, the step is at worst neutral (V-M-AS* vs V-M-AS: macro-F1 $d = +0.06$, $p = 0.840$; mAP $d = -0.26$, $p = 0.413$). Starting from ImageNet, the step significantly degrades mAP (V-M-IM: $d = -1.15$; V-C-IM: $d = -1.33$).

The interpretation of the distribution-axis result is constrained by a confound. Only the AudioSet contrast (V-M-AS*→V-M-AS) holds the framework constant

(MAE→MAE). Both ImageNet-referenced contrasts additionally switch from a supervised initialisation to a self-supervised framework, so their mAP degradation cannot be attributed to distribution shift alone. With this caveat, the cleanest in-study signal is that the in-domain pretraining step is tolerated when the source is same-modality (AudioSet) and harmful on mAP when it is cross-modality (ImageNet). This pattern aligns with the pretraining learning curves of Section VI-D: the ImageNet-initialised Audio-MAE run does not reach a lower reconstruction loss than the random-initialisation run, whereas the AudioSet-initialised run does. The reading is consistent with Huang *et al.*'s [14] finding that ImageNet initialisation underperforms random initialisation for the audio masked-reconstruction objective. A plausible explanation is that the objective relies on spectrogram-specific features that image priors do not supply. The contrastive triplet objective operates on global embedding similarity and transfers more readily from ImageNet, consistent with the faster, lower-converging loss curve of V-C-IM and its positive Group 1 result. Taken together, the answer to RQ2 is that transfer learning helps most as a direct initialisation, where the source modality is largely irrelevant at the median, while the value of continued in-domain pretraining depends on the source and is at best small on this dataset.

c) *RQ3: ViT-Base relative to the ResNet-50 baselines:* In its strongest setting (V-M-AS), ViT-Base reaches the highest macro-F1 median in the study (87.3%), essentially level with the supervised ResNet-50 baseline (R-B, 86.9%). On mAP the ordering is reversed: R-B attains the highest mAP of any configuration (97.6%). The ResNet-50 contrastive triplet encoder (R-C) under Recipe F significantly underperforms the supervised ResNet-50 baseline, in contrast to the result of [10]; Section VI-H shows that the same R-C encoder reaches a substantially higher macro-F1 under Recipe S than under Recipe F, so this underperformance is tied to the downstream recipe rather than to the encoder. Neither of the two cross-encoder differences (macro-F1 and mAP) is statistically tested, and the 0.4 pp macro-F1 margin lies within the run-to-run variance at this run count, so no encoder is shown to be superior overall. Because the two encoders are not parameter-matched (ViT-Base has roughly 86M parameters, Appendix H, against a markedly smaller ResNet-50), these observations describe the configurations as evaluated and are not architectural conclusions.

d) *Data scale and the supervised baseline:* The competitiveness of the supervised ResNet-50 baseline, and in particular its mAP lead, is best read in the light of the data regime. The used unlabeled ADSiM dataset contains approximately 47 500 recordings, which is small relative to the datasets on which transformer pretraining is usually shown to pay off, such as ImageNet [19] and AudioSet [18]. Large-scale pretraining is the regime in which Vision Transformers [12] and transformer-based audio encoders [14], [16], [36] typically rival or exceed convolutional baselines. Under this interpretation the strong R-B result is an expected consequence of the limited in-domain data available for self-supervised pretraining, rather

than a negative finding about self-supervised learning or transformer encoders as such. This is an interpretation rather than a tested claim. Whether a larger unlabeled dataset would narrow the gap is left to future work.

e) Methodological findings: Three further results bear on the interpretation of all of the above. First, the fine-tuning advantage reported by [10] is not robust under the dual-split protocol (Section VI-C): the cross-split effect reduces to $d = +0.10$, $p = 0.665$. Second, the downstream recipe is a non-negligible nuisance factor that must be held constant when comparing encoders (Section VI-H). On the ResNet-50 encoder, switching the recipe alone shifts macro-F1 by about 7 pp. Third, macro-F1 is significantly split-dependent across all supervised training runs, while mAP is not (Section VI-I).

f) Reproduction and small-sample variance: The reproduction (Section VI-C) recovers the qualitative patterns of [10] but not the statistical claims. The cross-split comparison gives $d = +0.10$, $p = 0.665$. The macro-F1 improvement of $0.916 \rightarrow 0.941$ reported by [10] was obtained on `ADSiM_S` alone with 5 runs per condition. The Monte-Carlo simulation of Appendix A predicts a macro-F1 standard deviation of about 2.3% on this split. Under that variance level, a difference of 2.5 pp between two five-run medians is consistent with random sampling. The observed standard deviations of the reproduction runs (1.4 to 1.8%) are systematically smaller than the simulated upper bound. The Monte-Carlo estimate is mildly conservative because it assumes a fixed accuracy of 0.90 rather than the empirical accuracy distribution. Empirical model accuracies cluster slightly higher, near 0.91, which mechanically lowers the variance and is consistent with the observed gap.

g) Batch size: In contrast to [24], batch size is not a leading hyperparameter for either self-supervised framework used here: the triplet pipeline samples negatives globally from the unlabeled dataset rather than within the batch, and the Audio-MAE objective is reconstruction-based and involves no in-batch comparison. The empirical check in Appendix I confirms this: increasing the batch size by a factor of 1.5 on `V-C-IM` and by a factor of 3 on `V-M-AS` leaves downstream performance statistically unchanged under the best-checkpoint protocol. The result is therefore a confirmation of an expectation rather than a finding.

h) Downstream-recipe sensitivity: The recipe comparison (Section VI-H) is a methodological control rather than a primary result: it isolates the downstream recipe from the encoder so that the gap between the reproduction under Recipe S and the main experiments under Recipe F can be attributed correctly. Holding the encoder fixed and changing only the recipe shifts the cross-split macro-F1 median by about 7.2 pp on the ResNet-50 `R-C` encoder (Recipe F to Recipe S) and by about 3.1 pp in the opposite direction on the `V-M-AS` encoder. A complementary descriptive contrast on the reproduced reference ResNet-50 encoder of Section VI-C (Appendix J) points the same way under heterogeneous seed protocols, and is therefore directional rather than a calibrated effect size. The direction of the recipe effect thus depends on

the encoder family, which indicates that recipe and encoder are not independent factors. The practical consequence for this work is limited and methodological: absolute macro-F1 values are recipe-dependent and should not be read as encoder-intrinsic, whereas the relative comparisons drawn under a single shared recipe (Recipe F) remain the valid basis for the conclusions. Because the recipe difference is a bundle of several simultaneous changes (Section VI-H, Appendix F-B), no single component is isolated.

i) Best-configuration synthesis: Read across the best-checkpoint configurations (Table XIII), the highest cross-split macro-F1 is reached by `V-M-AS` (87.3%, continued `AudioSet`→`ADSiM` Audio-MAE) and the highest mAP by the supervised `R-B` (97.6%). The transfer-initialised ViT-Base configurations (`V-M-AS`, `V-M-AS*`, `V-IM*`) cluster at the top of the macro-F1 ranking, above the `ADSiM`-only self-supervised configurations. This synthesis is descriptive. The differences within the transfer-initialised cluster are within the run-to-run variance at $n = 20$, the macro-F1 ranking is split-dependent (Section VI-I), and the comparison spans encoder families that are not parameter-matched. The synthesis therefore identifies promising configurations rather than a single controlled winner.

j) The split factor: The ANOVA confirms the assumption stated in Section VI-A: macro-F1 is significantly higher on `ADSiM_S` than on `ADSiM_N` (+3.8 pp on average; $\eta^2 = 0.145$). The same factor is not significant for mAP. That split choice explains about 14.5% of the macro-F1 variance is itself a substantive methodological result, and it provides the empirical justification for the dual-split design motivated in Section VI-A: a single split conflates genuine model quality with split-specific composition. The per-class F1 distributions in Figure 17 localise the effect to the small class *Curve Squeal*, whose F1 medians are systematically higher on `ADSiM_S` than on `ADSiM_N`, while the larger-class medians are comparable across splits. On `ADSiM_S` the real-run small-class F1 also exceeds the fixed-accuracy Monte-Carlo prediction, whereas on `ADSiM_N` it sits closer to it.

The most parsimonious account is sampling variance in the specific composition of the 14 *Curve Squeal* test instances, in line with the Monte-Carlo decomposition of Appendix A, in which about 66% of the macro-F1 variance is attributable to the smallest class. Whether the particular *Curve Squeal* instances in `ADSiM_S` are also intrinsically more separable, for example through a cleaner tonal signature, is a hypothesis that the present evidence does not establish. A targeted spectrogram comparison of the small-class instances across the two splits, inserted alongside Figure 17, would be required to test it.

k) Training dynamics: The training-dynamics analysis (Section VII) identifies the ImageNet-initialised continued-pretraining configurations (`V-M-IM` and `V-C-IM`) as the models with the widest train-validation gap. For these models the training macro-F1 approaches its ceiling while the validation macro-F1 saturates substantially lower and, for `V-C-IM`, declines slightly over the remaining budget. This is the stan-

standard signature of overfitting under a fixed Recipe F training budget. The pattern is consistent with the downstream results: $V-M-IM$ underperforms both the ADSiM-only $V-M$ (Group 1, directional) and the ImageNet transfer-only $V-IM^*$ (Group 2, significant on mAP), and the ImageNet-referenced continued configurations are the ones that degrade mAP in Section VI-G. Because Recipe F applies the same hyperparameters across all ViT configurations, the overfitting observed specifically for the strong ImageNet initialisations suggests that the learning-rate schedule may need to be adapted for strong initialisations on a small downstream set. This is an interpretation of the learning curves rather than a tested claim, and it is taken up as a future-work direction in Section VIII-D. A per-configuration recipe such as Recipe S, with reactive scheduling and multi-metric early stopping, can suppress this signature, at the cost of recipe transferability across encoders.

B. Relation to Prior Work

This work relates to two prior results on the same problem: the reference results of [10], [23] on the ADSiM dataset, and the Audio-MAE framework [14]. The audio-tagging perspective introduced for the secondary metric additionally connects to event-detection work on railway noise.

a) Comparison with the reference results: Schachinger *et al.* [10] report that contrastive triplet pretraining on a ResNet-50 encoder improves macro-F1 over a supervised baseline on `ADSiM_S` ($0.916 \rightarrow 0.941$, 5 runs per condition), and that MAE pretraining does not exceed the supervised baseline. This work extends their contrastive triplet framework from the original ResNet-50 encoder to a ViT-Base encoder ($V-C$, $V-C-IM$) and re-evaluates both encoder families under the dual-split, multi-seed protocol of Section VI-B. Under this protocol the contrastive triplet claim does not reproduce: the ResNet-50 reproduction (Section VI-C) reproduces the qualitative learning-curve pattern of the original pretraining run, namely the validation-loss collapse and the monotonic training-loss decrease, and produces a cross-split median in the same range, but the cross-split baseline-versus-fine-tuning effect is not significant ($d = +0.10$, $p = 0.665$). The contrastive triplet advantage reported by [10] is therefore not robust to the dual-split protocol used here.

Moving the framework to a transformer encoder does not by itself recover the effect either: contrastive triplet pretraining on the target dataset alone ($V-C$) does not significantly outperform its supervised ViT baseline on either metric (Section VI-E). A significant effect does emerge, however, once the framework is combined with transfer learning. Extending it on ViT with an ImageNet initialisation and continued in-domain pretraining ($V-C-IM$) significantly improves mAP over the ADSiM-only contrastive triplet encoder ($V-C$) ($+1.0$ pp, $d = +1.29$, $p < 0.001$; Section VI-G), with a directionally consistent macro-F1 gain that does not reach the corrected threshold ($+1.9$ pp, $d = +0.59$, $p = 0.068$). On a transformer encoder the contrastive objective of [10] is thus effective primarily as a refinement step on top of a transfer-learning initialisation rather than as a stand-alone procedure on the target dataset,

and even then the gain is statistically detectable only on the secondary metric, mAP.

The negative result for MAE is not reproduced. On ViT-Base, MAE pretraining on the target dataset ($V-M$) significantly outperforms its supervised baseline on both metrics ($+4.0$ pp macro-F1, $d = +1.02$; $+1.7$ pp mAP, $d = +2.13$). The encoder and the pretraining recipe differ at the same time between the two studies, and this work does not separate the two contributions, so the divergent MAE result cannot be attributed cleanly to either the encoder or the recipe.

b) Audio-MAE: As noted in the introduction (Chapter I), Audio-MAE is one of the standard self-supervised reference approaches for modern audio classification, established in the broader audio domain rather than on railway sound specifically. Huang *et al.* [14] report that AudioSet pretraining transfers effectively across a range of downstream audio classification tasks, and that ImageNet initialisation provides a weaker starting point for the masked-reconstruction objective than random initialisation in the audio setting. The results obtained here are consistent with both observations and extend them from the pretraining loss curves to the downstream metrics on the railway domain.

On the pretraining side, the AudioSet-initialised run ($V-M-AS$) converges faster and reaches a lower reconstruction loss in the early epochs, whereas the ImageNet-initialised run ($V-M-IM$) does not improve on the random-initialisation loss (Section VI-D). These learning-curve patterns carry over to the downstream task. AudioSet remains the most useful source for the masked-reconstruction objective, with $V-M-AS$ attaining the highest cross-split macro-F1 median in the study (87.3%; Table XIII), while the weaker ImageNet starting point degrades downstream performance: the ImageNet-continued variant ($V-M-IM$) significantly loses mAP relative to the ImageNet transfer-only initialisation ($d = -1.15$; Section VI-G). Even from random initialisation the objective transfers to this domain, with $V-M$ significantly outperforming the supervised ViT baseline on both metrics (Section VI-E). Taken together, these results reaffirm Audio-MAE as a reliable reference approach beyond the benchmarks on which it was originally established, now also on railway environmental sound.

c) Audio-tagging perspective of mAP: This work introduces mean average precision as a secondary, audio-tagging-oriented view of model performance on the railway recordings (Section VI-B). This perspective connects to event-detection work on railway noise, where Betton-Ployon *et al.* [9] apply an AudioSet-pretrained classifier to detect vehicle-like events in long-term recordings. A tagging-style metric is operationally closer to that detection setting than single-label macro-F1, because it scores the ranking of class presence rather than a single hard decision [18], [30]. The mAP results reported here should be read as a complementary, detection-oriented signal and not as a direct measurement of event-detection performance on continuous recordings, which is outside the scope of the segmented classification task studied here.

C. Limitations

a) Hyperparameter tuning of Recipe F and Recipe B:

The recipes designed in this work (Appendix F) follow established conventions for AdamW, half-cosine scheduling, layer-wise learning-rate decay, and class-weighted cross-entropy, but were not subject to a systematic hyperparameter sweep. The recipe experiment in Section VI-H shows that downstream-recipe choices alone can shift macro-F1 by about 7 pp on the same encoder under a shared protocol. The absolute macro-F1 numbers reported under Recipe F should therefore be read as a lower bound rather than an upper bound on what the corresponding encoders can achieve. The relative comparisons between self-supervised configurations under a shared recipe remain interpretable.

b) *Run count:* Each configuration was evaluated with 10 seeds per split, giving 20 runs in the cross-split sample. At this run count, effects of $|d| < 0.4$ are not robustly detectable, and medium effects in the range $0.5 \leq |d| < 0.8$ are detectable only marginally. Several Group 1 and Group 2 comparisons in this range, such as V-M versus V-M-AS on macro-F1 ($d = +0.51$), do not reach significance under the best-checkpoint protocol despite being directionally consistent with the mAP result on the same comparison. Their non-significance should not be read as evidence of absence.

c) *Independence assumption:* The cross-split sample combines the runs from ADSIM_N and ADSIM_S into a single sample for the t -tests. Two properties of this construction qualify the reported p -values. First, the two splits differ systematically in difficulty (Section VI-I), so the pooled sample is a mixture of two non-identical distributions rather than draws from one population, which weakens the identically-distributed assumption underlying the pooled t -test. Second, for the pretrained configurations all runs share a single selected pretraining checkpoint and differ only in the downstream fine-tuning seed; the runs are therefore not independent realisations of the complete pretraining-plus-fine-tuning pipeline, and the variability contributed by the pretraining step is not represented in the sample. These two properties bias the test in opposite directions, the split mixture conservatively by widening the within-group spread and the shared checkpoint anti-conservatively by omitting pretraining variability, so the net effect on the reported p -values is not determined a priori and they should be read as approximate. Modelling the split as an explicit factor, for example through a two-way analysis, or drawing an independent pretraining checkpoint per run, would address both points more rigorously.

d) *Architectural comparison:* This work does not pursue a parameter-matched ViT-Base-versus-ResNet-50 comparison. The two encoders differ substantially in capacity (ViT-Base has roughly 86M parameters, Appendix H). Statements that involve both encoder families, such as the observation that V-M-AS reaches a marginally higher cross-split macro-F1 median than R-B, should not be read as architectural conclusions.

e) Encoder-recipe confound in the MAE comparison:

The divergence from [10] on the MAE objective, where MAE pretraining underperforms the supervised baseline on

the ResNet-50 setup of [10] but outperforms it on the ViT-Base setup of this work (Section VIII-B), cannot be attributed to a single cause. The two studies differ simultaneously in the encoder architecture (ResNet-50 versus ViT-Base) and in the supervised-training recipe (Recipe S versus Recipe F), and the present design varies both factors at once. Because the two changes are confounded, the experiment cannot isolate whether the reversal originates from the transformer encoder, from the modernised downstream recipe, or from their interaction. The MAE result of this work should therefore be read as evidence that the combination of a ViT-Base encoder and Recipe F yields a positive MAE effect on ADSiM, not as evidence about either factor in isolation. A parameter- and recipe-matched comparison that varies one factor at a time would be required to separate the contributions.

f) *Recipe transfer and bundle effect:* The recipe-effect experiment (Section VI-H) approximates rather than literally transfers Recipe S, since spectrogram shape, validation-time crop length, and tensor orientation cannot be transferred without retraining the encoder. The retained components are listed in Section VI-H. Beyond this approximation, the experiment switches the recipe as a single bundle and does not separate which of the differing components drives the observed shift. Statements such as the recipe alone produces a 7.2 pp shift should be read as statements about the recipe as a whole, not as causal claims about any single component.

g) *Pretraining-dataset distribution:* The unlabeled ADSiM dataset is dominated by *Curve 1* (71.8%), while the downstream task uses three other locations. The pipeline is therefore an in-domain, out-of-distribution scenario rather than an in-domain, in-distribution one. The small marginal contribution of continued in-domain pretraining observed in Section VI-G should be read in this light.

h) *Best-checkpoint selection:* For every configuration with a pretraining-epoch grid, the reported result is the checkpoint with the best cross-split median on the evaluation metric (Section VI-E). Because the pretraining epoch is selected on the same cross-split metric that is then reported, the per-configuration medians are optimistic estimates of each configuration’s achievable performance and the associated p -values are anti-conservative. The bias is not uniform across comparisons: configurations that possess a pretraining-epoch grid (the ADSiM-pretrained and continued-pretraining configurations) are favoured relative to references that do not (the supervised-from-scratch baselines and the external transfer-only initialisations), so the self-supervised-versus-baseline gains (Section VI-E) and the continued-versus-transfer-only contrasts (Group 2, Section VI-G) may be overstated. Comparisons in which both sides are selected identically (Group 1) are less affected, and the reproduction (Section VI-C) is unaffected because it selects the checkpoint by matching the original loss curve rather than the downstream metric. An unbiased estimate would require selecting the pretraining checkpoint on an independent signal, rather than on the reported cross-split metric. The rankings reported here should therefore be read as indicative rather than calibrated.

i) From limitations to future directions: These limitations are not independent. The absence of a recipe sweep, the recipe-encoder coupling, the marginal value of in-domain continued pretraining, and the overfitting of the strong ImageNet initialisations all point toward the same next step, namely a more controlled optimisation of the downstream recipe and the pretraining-dataset composition. Section VIII-D develops these directions.

D. Implications and Outlook

a) Evaluation protocol: The dual-split, multi-seed protocol (Section VI-B) is required to detect effects on the order of 1 to 3 pp macro-F1 on the ADSiM task. A single split with a small run count does not separate genuine model improvements from sampling variance in the small-class composition. Future work on ADSiM should adopt at least the dual-split protocol used here. A third independent split would strengthen the variance estimate and would also relax the independence concern raised in Section VIII-C.

b) Choice of primary metric: The split-effect analysis (Section VI-I) shows that mAP is significantly less split-dependent than macro-F1 on this task. macro-F1 is retained as the primary metric in this work for comparability with [10], but for future work on ADSiM that is not bound by direct comparability, mAP should be considered as the primary metric.

c) Recipe-encoder coupling: The recipe experiment indicates that downstream-recipe decisions and encoder decisions are not independent factors. A future iteration could perform a per-configuration hyperparameter search on Recipe F and report the resulting per-configuration optima. This is likely to compress the spread between configurations and to particularly benefit the models whose Recipe F training dynamics show overfitting (Section VII).

d) Learning-rate schedules for strong initialisations: The overfitting observed for the ImageNet-initialised continued-pretraining configurations under a shared Recipe F (Section VII) suggests that strong initialisations on a small downstream set may require a dedicated learning-rate schedule, for example a lower peak learning rate, stronger layer-wise decay, or a shorter budget. Tuning the learning-rate schedule for these configurations is a concrete future-work direction that follows directly from the learning curves.

e) Disentangling the contributing factors: Several findings in this work are entangled by design: encoder family and pretraining recipe in the comparison with [10], [23], recipe components within the recipe bundle, checkpoint selection across configurations, and the test-split factor. A future study that varies these factors one at a time under a fully identical evaluation protocol, with multiple encoders per family, would allow a cleaner attribution of encoder, recipe, checkpoint, and split effects than the present design supports.

f) Pretraining design: Two directions follow from the self-supervised and transfer-learning results. First, the case for ADSiM-dataset pretraining is strongest for random-initialisation Audio-MAE (V-M) and weakest when the pre-

training sits on top of a strong transfer source. A future study could examine whether a larger ADSiM unlabeled dataset narrows or eliminates this gap. Second, the present pretraining is in-domain but out-of-distribution, since the unlabeled dataset is location-imbalanced relative to the downstream locations. A more controlled in-domain, in-distribution variant, restricting pretraining to recordings from the locations represented in the downstream task, would isolate the distribution-shift contribution.

IX. CONCLUSION

Railway noise pollution is an increasing concern, and recent interest in event-based noise indicators raises the need for automatic methods that identify and characterise individual train pass-bys [7], [8]. Within that broader pipeline, this work studied the representation-learning problem underlying the classification of segmented railway sound events. The Introduction identified a gap: transformer-based spectrogram encoders and the role of different transfer-learning strategies had not been systematically evaluated for railway sound classification, where existing studies remained convolution-based and were limited by weak labels, class imbalance, and small evaluation samples. This work addressed the gap with three contributions: a methodological foundation under which downstream claims can be tested reliably, a controlled evaluation of two self-supervised frameworks on a ViT-Base encoder across several transfer-learning sources, and an analysis of how recipe-side and encoder-side decisions interact.

The methodological foundation rests on the dual-split, multi-seed evaluation protocol, a contrastive triplet procedure with consistent train and validation augmentation and training-loss-based checkpoint selection (Section IV-C), and the Monte-Carlo characterisation of the test-split variance. Under this foundation, the fine-tuning advantage reported by [10] does not separate the baseline and fine-tuning conditions in the cross-split sample ($d = +0.10$, $p = 0.665$); the reproduction recovers the qualitative learning-curve pattern of that pretraining run but not the statistical claim.

The substantive findings answer the three research questions. For RQ1, Audio-MAE on a ViT-Base encoder achieves the strongest downstream performance among the self-supervised frameworks evaluated and is the only ADSiM-only configuration to significantly outperform its supervised baseline on both metrics; contrastive triplet pretraining on the target dataset does not. For RQ2, transfer learning provides a large benefit on the ADSiM downstream task, with AudioSet and ImageNet indistinguishable at the available run count when used as a direct initialisation. When used as a starting point for continued in-domain pretraining, a benefit becomes statistically detectable only on the secondary metric, mAP, for the AudioSet→ADSiM Audio-MAE and ImageNet→ADSiM contrastive triplet configurations, while on macro-F1 the same comparisons remain directionally consistent without reaching significance. For RQ3, the ViT-Base encoder family behaves consistently across the evaluated settings; its strongest configuration (V-M-AS, continued AudioSet→ADSiM Audio-MAE)

reaches the highest macro-F1 median (87.3%), marginally above the supervised ResNet-50 baseline (86.9%), a difference that is neither statistically tested nor outside the run-to-run variance.

One result qualifies the case for self-supervised learning and should be stated explicitly. The supervised ResNet-50 baseline (R-B) attains the highest mAP of any configuration in the study (97.6%) and the second-highest macro-F1 (86.9%). On the secondary, detection-oriented metric, no self-supervised or transfer-based configuration exceeds this supervised baseline at the median. This is consistent with the limited scale of the in-domain unlabeled dataset relative to the large-scale datasets on which transformer pretraining typically pays off, and indicates that the absolute benefit of self-supervised pretraining on this task is bounded by the data regime.

A separate, methodological observation concerns the downstream recipe. On a fixed ResNet-50 encoder the recipe alone shifts macro-F1 by about 7 pp under a shared protocol, and the direction of the shift depends on the encoder family. This is a nuisance factor rather than a result of interest: it means that absolute numbers obtained under a single shared recipe are recipe-dependent and cannot be optimised independently of the encoder, while the relative comparisons drawn under that shared recipe remain valid.

Within the limits set out in the discussion, in particular the absence of a systematic recipe sweep, the in-domain but out-of-distribution character of the unlabeled dataset, and the pooled cross-split sample, this work provides a set of validated reference results and a reusable evaluation protocol for the ADSiM task. The most promising future directions follow directly from the results and limitations: a per-configuration optimisation of the downstream recipe, including learning-rate schedules adapted to strong initialisations on a small downstream set; a cleaner separation of encoder, recipe, checkpoint, and split effects under an identical protocol; a controlled in-domain, in-distribution variant of the ADSiM pretraining; an evaluation on a larger unlabeled dataset; and the use of mean average precision as the primary evaluation metric, given its substantially lower split-dependency. A reliable acoustic-monitoring pipeline of the kind targeted by the ADSiM project will benefit from each of these, alongside the encoder, self-supervised, and transfer-learning combinations identified here.

X. AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Ivan Birkmaier conducted the research as part of the master’s thesis, including study conception, data collection, analysis, and drafting of the manuscript. Georg Brandmayr supervised the research process on a regular basis, provided conceptual guidance, critically reviewed the manuscript, and approved the final version for publication.

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To quantify how strongly the macro-F1 fluctuates due to sampling variance in the test set alone — in the complete absence of any model-to-model differences — a Monte Carlo simulation [37] was conducted. For each of the split configurations, 10 000 synthetic test-set evaluations were generated by drawing per-class predictions from a multinomial distribution with a fixed true accuracy of 0.90, using the real test-set class sizes. As an additional reference condition, ADSIM_F, a hypothetical fully class-balanced split (118 samples per class, which does not correspond to a realistic data regime), was simulated to isolate the effect of class imbalance. From each simulated confusion matrix, per-class F1 scores and the macro-F1 were computed. The central findings of the simulation are:

- First, ADSIM_S and ADSIM_N produce nearly identical simulated distributions — an expected result, since the splits differ only marginally in their class-size proportions (see Figure 8). The standard deviation of the simulated macro-F1 closely matches the observed between-run standard deviation of the real training runs and is substantially higher than that of the class-balanced ADSIM_F condition. This demonstrates that the high run-to-run variance observed in the real experiments is largely explained by sampling variance induced by the class-imbalanced test sets, rather than by instabilities in the training procedure.
- Second, this variance is dominated by the smallest class. Approximately 66 % of the total macro-F1 variance originates from the smallest class (*Curve Squeal*, $n = 14$), whereas in the balanced ADSIM_F condition the variance is distributed evenly across all four classes (Figure 8). A substantial portion of the observed between-split differences can therefore be attributed to the stochastic composition of the small classes rather than to genuine differences in model quality.

APPENDIX B
PCA ANALYSIS

This appendix provides the full methodology and quantitative loadings underlying the PCA characterisation summarised in Section VI-A.

a) *Feature Extraction and Preprocessing*: A 2D PCA was computed on a set of scale-invariant audio features. The features were extracted on a GPU-accelerated pipeline from mel-spectrograms ($n_{\text{fft}} = 2048$, hop length 512, $n_{\text{mels}} = 128$) after all recordings had been resampled to a uniform target sample rate of 32 kHz. The feature set covers energy and dynamics descriptors (RMS energy, peak-to-RMS, sub-band energies), spectral shape descriptors (*spectral centroid*, *bandwidth*, *rolloff*, *flatness*), temporal structure descriptors (*zero-crossing rate*, *spectral novelty*, *onset density*), and frequency stability and harmonicity descriptors (*frequency stability*, *a harmonicity proxy*, *spectral contrast*). Prior to the decomposition, the features were standardised to zero mean and unit variance. Since *Curve 1* dominates the dataset in absolute

Feature	PC1	PC2
spectral_centroid	0.334	0.424
spectral_bandwidth	0.296	0.452
spectral_rolloff	0.503	0.070
spectral_flatness	-0.374	0.317
zcr	0.475	0.174
dynamics_range	-0.188	0.443
spectral_novelty	0.208	-0.428
spectral_contrast	0.321	-0.318

TABLE XIV: PCA loadings of the first two principal components. PC1 and PC2 account for 44.3% and 31.3% of the feature variance, respectively.

counts, a sample of up to 1500 files per location was drawn to ensure that the projection reflects acoustic structure rather than sampling frequency. The resulting balanced subset contains $n = 7090$ recordings.

b) Post-hoc Overlays: To go beyond a purely location-based visualisation, the same PCA fit is shown with four explanatory overlays (Figure 6): (a) recording location, (b) track geometry (curve vs. straight), (c) recording duration in seconds, and (d) a loudness proxy defined as $20 \log_{10}(\text{RMS} + \epsilon)$ in dB. The overlays are *not* inputs to the decomposition; they are plotted on top of the fixed projection to characterise which physical and operational factors structure the acoustic feature space. The loudness proxy is reported as an RMS level in dB; calibrated $L_{A,eq}$ values were not available for the dataset.

c) Interpretation of the Principal Axes: The first two principal components together explain 75.6% of the feature variance (Table XIV). PC1 is dominated by positive loadings on *spectral rolloff* (0.503), *zero-crossing rate* (0.475), *spectral centroid* (0.334), and *spectral contrast* (0.321), and a strong negative loading on *spectral flatness* (-0.374). PC1 can therefore be read as a *brightness/structure* axis: high values correspond to high-frequency, tonally structured signals, while low values correspond to dull, broadband recordings. PC2 contrasts the energy- and shape-oriented features *spectral bandwidth* (0.452), *dynamics range* (0.443), and *spectral centroid* (0.424) against the transient-sensitive *spectral novelty* (-0.428) and *spectral contrast* (-0.318), and thus separates *broadband stationary* content (positive PC2) from *transient, impulsive* content (negative PC2).

d) Findings from the Overlays: The four overlays in Figure 6 yield a consistent and complementary picture of the dataset:

- **Location (panel a).** *Curve 1, Curve 2, Curve 3, and Curve 4* overlap substantially in a common dense region near the origin; their centroids lie within a small neighbourhood and their 1.5σ ellipses are largely concentric. *Straight 1* forms a clearly separated cluster in the lower-left quadrant. This is consistent with its markedly lower spectral centroid (median ≈ 2 mel bins compared with 17–28 for the four curve locations) and is plausibly explained by the combination of its distinctive sample rate (51.2 kHz) and its installation at straight track sections.

- **Track geometry (panel b).** Collapsing the five locations to the binary *curve* vs. *straight* contrast shows that the separation observed in panel (a) is not driven by location identity but by the underlying track geometry. The straight-track cluster is shifted towards lower PC2 and slightly lower PC1, in line with the absence of rolling-noise modulation typical for curves.
- **Recording duration (panel c).** A clear gradient along PC1 is visible: short recordings (dark purple, <10 s) concentrate at low PC1 values, while long recordings (yellow, >30 s) populate the high-PC1 region. Since PC1 is a brightness/structure axis, longer pass-by events tend to integrate more high-frequency, tonally structured content — consistent with longer trains exposing the microphone to a richer mixture of wheel–rail interaction phenomena.
- **Loudness proxy (panel d).** The RMS-based loudness proxy spans roughly 30 dB across the dataset and aligns predominantly with PC2: louder recordings concentrate in the lower half of the projection, partially overlapping the region occupied by *Straight 1*. PC2 therefore carries a substantial loudness component on top of its broadband-vs.-transient interpretation.

e) Implications for the Downstream Task: Three points follow from this characterisation and are picked up in Section VI-A. First, the dominant structural contrast in acoustic feature space is *curve* versus *straight* track geometry, not location identity within the curve group — which supports framing the SSL pretraining as a domain-transfer scenario in which the four curve locations form a coherent source domain and *Straight 1* contributes acoustically distinct, supporting variability. Second, recording duration and loudness are non-trivial explanatory factors: each of them accounts for a visible portion of the variance captured by PC1 and PC2, and both vary by roughly an order of magnitude across the dataset (a few seconds to over 40 s; ~ 30 dB). Spectrogram construction, input-length policy, and amplitude normalisation must therefore be chosen to remain robust under these ranges. Third, neither overlay produces a cleanly separated cluster orthogonal to the location structure, which suggests that duration and loudness are intertwined with train type and pass-by speed rather than acting as independent nuisance dimensions.

APPENDIX C VALIDATION LOSS DEGENERACY

This appendix provides the formal degeneracy analysis referenced in Section IV-C.

If the CTL validation loss is computed without the stochastic augmentations applied during training, anchor–positive pairs exhibit artificially high similarity. Even when anchor and positive differ slightly due to a random temporal crop offset [10], the dominant augmentation operations are absent, biasing the validation loss significantly downward.

The magnitude of this bias can be made precise by considering the limiting case $\mathbf{p}_i = \mathbf{a}_i$, where cosine similarity attains its maximum $\text{sim}(\mathbf{a}_i, \mathbf{p}_i) = 1$. Substituting into the triplet loss (Eq. 2) yields

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{clean}} = \max\left(m - \frac{1}{\tau} + \frac{\text{sim}(\mathbf{a}_i, \mathbf{n}_i)}{\tau}, 0\right), \quad (3)$$

which is zero whenever $\text{sim}(\mathbf{a}_i, \mathbf{n}_i) < 1 - m\tau$. With $m = 0.5$ and $\tau = 0.07$, this threshold evaluates to 0.965. Since negatives drawn from different recordings typically have cosine similarities well below this value, $\mathcal{L}_{\text{clean}} = 0$ for virtually all triplets, regardless of the encoder’s actual discriminative quality.

When only a small crop offset separates anchor and positive, the loss does not collapse to exactly zero (see Figure 9), but since the encoder is never required to be invariant to anything stronger than a temporal shift, anchor-positive similarity remains close to 1 and the aggregate loss converges toward a floor determined by crop-offset statistics rather than encoder quality.

When the positive is an independently augmented view, $\text{sim}(\mathbf{a}_i, \mathbf{p}_i) = s_p < 1$ with s_p strictly bounded away from 1, and the zero-condition tightens to $\text{sim}(\mathbf{a}_i, \mathbf{n}_i) < s_p - m\tau$. Many more triplets then remain active, and the validation signal faithfully reflects the encoder’s representational quality.

APPENDIX D

PRETRAINING HYPERPARAMETERS

This appendix reports the pretraining hyperparameter recipes used in this work and for the reproduction of [10]. Table XV summarises the hyperparameters for the Audio-MAE (ViT-only) and CTL experiments. Slash-separated entries indicate alternative values applied, mapped to concrete configurations (Chapter IV) in Table XVI.

a) Optimisation details: All pretraining runs use AdamW. The momentum coefficients (β_1, β_2) define the exponential moving averages of the gradient and squared gradient; following Audio-MAE [14], pretraining uses (0.9, 0.95).

b) Learning-rate schedule: Training starts with a linear warmup from 0 to the base learning rate over the specified number of warmup epochs, followed by half-cosine decay to a minimum learning rate of 10^{-6} .

c) Weight-decay exclusion: Weight decay is not applied to positional embeddings, class tokens, normalisation parameters, biases, or learnable attention-temperature parameters, including τ in shifted local attention.

d) Effective learning-rate scaling: For ViT-based pretraining, the learning rate follows the Audio-MAE batch-size scaling rule [14]:

$$\text{lr}_{\text{eff}} = \text{lr}_{\text{base}} \times \frac{\text{batch size}}{256}. \quad (4)$$

e) Configuration-specific hyperparameters: Random-initialisation pretraining runs receive a larger epoch budget and higher learning rates than continued-pretraining runs. For the ViT-Base contrastive triplet pretraining (V-C) on random initialisation, the patch-projection layer was frozen and the weight decay was increased relative to the other ViT contrastive runs, following the stability prescriptions of

MoCo v3 [38]. The ResNet-50 contrastive run uses a higher learning rate than the ViT runs, consistent with the inductive-bias difference between CNNs and ViTs [12].

A. Reproduction Recipe

The CTL configuration of [10] is summarised in Table XVII. The key design choices that distinguish it from the recipes used in this work are: a plain Adam optimiser without weight decay, the absence of a pretraining scheduler, a non-zero projection-head dropout, and reliance on the (degenerate) validation loss for checkpoint selection.

APPENDIX E

DOWNSTREAM HYPERPARAMETERS

This section documents the downstream-task hyperparameters of Recipes B and F, as well as Recipe S, which is used for the reproduction of [10]. It further describes the design differences between Recipes B, F, and S.

APPENDIX F

RECIPE B AND F

Table XVIII provides a side-by-side comparison of Recipes B and F. Recipe F is split into two columns for ResNet-50 and ViT-Base because the two encoders use distinct optimisation settings.

a) Optimiser and Scheduler: Recipes B and F use AdamW with $(\beta_1, \beta_2) = (0.9, 0.999)$, in contrast to the $\beta_2 = 0.95$ used during pretraining; this follows He *et al.* [15], where a smaller β_2 is recommended for pretraining and the standard $\beta_2 = 0.999$ is used for downstream fine-tuning. AdamW’s decoupled weight decay is the established default for Transformer-based encoders and removes the implicit interaction between learning rate and L_2 regularisation present in Adam [39].

The half-cosine schedule, preceded by a linear warmup, provides a deterministic, monotonically decaying schedule that is independent of validation-loss noise. This is particularly relevant on the class-imbalanced ADSiM labeled dataset, where validation loss has been observed to be a noisy training signal (see also the Monte-Carlo analysis in Appendix A).

b) Learning-Rate Strategy: Recipe F uses substantially smaller base learning rates than Recipe B because the pre-trained representations should be preserved and only adapted selectively to the downstream task.

For ViT-Base, Recipe F additionally applies layer-wise learning-rate decay (LLDR) with a factor of 0.80 and a head learning-rate multiplier of 5. LLDR is the standard fine-tuning convention for ViT-based architectures [15]: it protects early-layer features (which encode general spectro-temporal patterns) while allowing the later layers and the head to adapt more aggressively. ResNet-50 fine-tuning in Recipe F omits LLDR.

Element	Audio-MAE	CTL (ViT)	CTL (ResNet-50)
Audio frontend		32 kHz, 128 Mel, hop 512	
Shape		[1, 448, 128]	
Norm. (μ, σ)		$\mu = -3.09, \sigma = 4.82$	
Optimiser (β_1, β_2)		AdamW (0.9, 0.95)	
Scheduler		Half-cosine + linear warmup	
Seed		96	
Precision		FP32	
Min. LR		10^{-6}	
Batch Size		32	
Warmup (epochs)	4/7/10	10/30	10
Pretext task	MSE	Triplet	Triplet
τ / m	- / -	0.07 / 0.5	0.07 / 0.5
Masking	80% random	time + freq.	time + freq.
Weight decay	10^{-4}	0.05/0.1	0.01
LR Scaling	True	True	False
Base LR	0.0008/0.0010/0.0016	$1 \times 10^{-4} / 4 \times 10^{-4}$	2×10^{-4}
Epochs	30/75/120	175/250	150

TABLE XV: Pretraining hyperparameters

Config	Base LR	Weight Decay	Warmup (ep)	Epochs
V-M	1.6×10^{-3}	1.0×10^{-4}	7	120
V-M-IM	8.0×10^{-4}	1.0×10^{-4}	10	30
V-M-AS	1.0×10^{-3}	1.0×10^{-4}	4	75
V-C	4.0×10^{-4}	1.0×10^{-1}	30	250
V-C-IM	1.0×10^{-4}	5.0×10^{-2}	10	200
R-C	2.0×10^{-4}	1.0×10^{-2}	10	150

TABLE XVI: Per-configuration pretraining hyperparameters. Remaining settings shared across configurations are in table XV.

Parameter	Value
Type	Adam
Base learning rate	1×10^{-4a}
Weight decay	0
Pretext task	Triplet
Margin m / temperature τ	0.5 / 0.07
Monitor metric	Validation loss ^b
Projection-head dropout	0.5
Seed	96

TABLE XVII: Reproduction pretraining hyperparameters

^aNo explicit pretraining LR scheduler is used.

^bAs shown Section IV-C monitoring of a validation loss was applied.

c) Loss Weighting: Recipes B and F use class weights [1, 1, 5, 3], providing a 3–5× stronger gradient signal for the minority classes (*Curve Squeal* and *Both*) in line with the class distribution analysis in Section VI-A. This choice directly targets macro-F1, the primary evaluation metric of this work, which weights all four classes equally regardless of their frequency.

d) Validation Protocol: Recipes B and F evaluate on fixed-length spectrograms with a target frame length of 944 with a uniform centre crop and a batch size of 32. The fixed-length protocol is required because ViT positional embeddings are interpolated for a fixed target patch grid; allowing variable-length inputs would require re-interpolating the embeddings on every batch, which is computationally prohibitive at validation time. The same fixed-length protocol is applied consistently to

ResNet-50 in Recipes B and F to keep validation comparable across encoder families.

e) Classification-Head Architecture: Recipes B and F use a three-layer classification head [encoder_dim, 512, 256] before the final classifier, where encoder_dim = 2048 for ResNet-50 and encoder_dim = 768 for ViT-Base. The head architecture is therefore held constant across all encoders up to the input dimension of the first hidden layer.

f) Early Stopping: Recipes B and F monitor only validation macro-F1 with patience 15 epochs and min_delta = 0.005. The single-metric criterion aligns the early-stopping signal directly with the primary evaluation metric. Monitoring multiple correlated metrics in parallel can extend training beyond the point at which the primary metric has plateaued, increasing the probability that random validation-set fluctuations trigger an additional training window [28]; tying early stopping to a single, clearly defined primary metric avoids this implicit selection effect.

The relatively generous patience value of 15 is motivated by the Monte-Carlo simulation in Appendix A: the validation set is small and class-imbalanced, which causes macro-F1 to fluctuate strongly between epochs due to sampling variance in the smallest class. A patience of 15 provides sufficient room for the model to recover from such stochastic dips without prematurely terminating training. The minimum delta of 0.005 ensures that only meaningful improvements, corresponding to at least 0.5% in macro-F1, reset the patience counter, thereby filtering out noise-driven micro-improvements that do not reflect genuine learning progress.

Parameter	Recipe B		Recipe F	
	ResNet-50	ViT-Base	ResNet-50	ViT-Base
Seeds	10 seeds: {42, 123, 256, 512, 768, 1024, 2048, 4096, 8192, 16384}			
cudnn_backend	deterministic			
Epochs	70	70	50	50
Optimiser (β_1, β_2)	AdamW	AdamW	AdamW (0.9, 0.999)	AdamW
Weight decay	0.01	0.05	0.01	0.01
Scheduler	half-cosine	half-cosine	half-cosine	half-cosine
Warmup epochs	8	8	4	5
Min. LR	10^{-8}	10^{-8}	10^{-8}	10^{-8}
Base LR	5×10^{-5}	1×10^{-3}	5×10^{-6}	5×10^{-4}
LR scaling (BS / ref BS 256)	False	True	False	True
Layer-wise LR decay	—	0.65	—	0.80
Head LR multiplier	1	10	1	5
Criterion	Cross-entropy, class weights [1, 1, 5, 3]			
Tensor layout	BCTF			
Frame target length	944 (fixed)			
Mel norm.	True			
wav-level (volume, noise)	rate 0.2 each			
SpecAugment (freq / time rate)	0.8 / 0.8			
freq. mask	10			
time mask	50			
Batch size (val/test)	32, fixed-length crop			
Monitored metric	macro-F1			
Patience (epochs)	15			
Patience min. Δ	0.005			
Classification head				
Hidden layers	[embedding dim, 512, 256, classes]			

TABLE XVIII: Downstream-task recipes used in this work: Recipe B (*Baseline from scratch*) and Recipe F (*Finetuning*). Recipe F is split into a ResNet-50 column and a ViT-Base column.

g) *ResNet-50 in Recipe B*: The ResNet-50 entry of Recipe B uses a base learning rate of 5×10^{-5} rather than the 1×10^{-3} shared by ViT-Base, omits the linear LR scaling, and uses a smaller weight decay of 0.01 instead of 0.05. This configuration was identified empirically: an initial ResNet-50 from-scratch run at 1×10^{-5} exhibited strong underfitting, and increasing the base learning rate to 5×10^{-5} together with reducing the weight decay was identified as the configuration that closed this gap and made R-B competitive with the ViT baselines on cross-split macro-F1.

A. Recipe S

Recipe S is summarised in Table XIX.

B. Comparison: Recipes B/F and S

The differences between (B, F) and S are not isolated parameter changes but reflect a coherent shift in pipeline philosophy. The most consequential differences, together with the rationale for each modernisation in B and F, are summarised below.

a) *Optimiser and scheduler*: Recipe S uses Adam with zero weight decay and a reactive ReduceLRonPlateau scheduler that decays the learning rate by a factor of 0.6 after 6 epochs without improvement on validation loss. Recipes B and F replace this with AdamW (decoupled weight decay of 0.01–0.05) and a half-cosine schedule with explicit warmup and a low minimum-learning-rate floor of 10^{-8} .

b) *Learning-rate strategy*: Recipe S applies a split learning rate, training the encoder at 3×10^{-4} and the classification head at 8×10^{-4} , treating the pretrained encoder and the randomly initialised head as two separate parameter groups with hand-tuned learning rates. Recipe F instead uses a single base learning rate (substantially smaller at 5×10^{-6} for ResNet-50 and 5×10^{-4} for ViT) and, for ViT-Base encoders, adds layer-wise learning-rate decay with a factor of 0.80 and a head learning-rate multiplier of 5. Layer-wise decay is the standard fine-tuning convention for ViT-based architectures [14], [15] and protects early-layer features (which encode general spectro-temporal patterns) while allowing the later layers and the head to adapt more aggressively. ResNet-50 fine-tuning in Recipe F omits layer-wise decay.

c) *Loss weighting*: Recipe S uses unweighted cross-entropy. Recipes B and F use class weights [1, 1, 5, 3], providing a 3–5 \times stronger gradient signal for the minority classes (*Curve Squeal* and *Both*) in line with the class distribution analysis in Section VI-A. This choice directly targets macro-F1 – the primary evaluation metric of this work — which weights all four classes equally regardless of their frequency.

d) *Validation protocol*: Recipe S evaluates on full-length, variable-duration samples with a batch size of 1, applying neither cropping nor padding at validation and test time. Recipes B and F evaluate on a fixed frame target length of

Parameter	Value
Split seed	96 (data partition only; runs otherwise unseeded)
Run repetitions	20 per split (non-deterministic)
cuda_backend	default (non-deterministic)
Epochs	120
Optimiser	Adam
Weight decay	0.0
(β_1, β_2)	(0.9, 0.999)
Scheduler	ReduceLRonPlateau
Mode / factor / patience	min / 0.6 / 6
Encoder LR	3×10^{-4}
Head LR	8×10^{-4}
Criterion	Cross-entropy, unweighted
Tensor layout	BCFT
Duration Seconds (train)	15
Duration Seconds (test/val)	variable (full-length)
wav-level (volume, noise)	disabled
SpecAugment (freq / time rate)	1.0 / 1.0
freq. mask	7
time mask	50
Batch size (val/test)	1, full-length sample
Monitored metrics	loss + accuracy + macro-F1 (<code>require_all</code>)
Patience (epochs)	7
Patience min. Δ	0.0
Hidden layers	[2048, 512, 256]

TABLE XIX: Recipe S of [10], used in this work exclusively for reproduction.

944 with a uniform crop and a batch size of 32. The fixed-length protocol is required because ViT positional embeddings are interpolated for a fixed target patch grid; allowing variable-length inputs would require re-interpolating the embeddings on every batch, which is computationally prohibitive at validation time. The same fixed-length protocol is applied consistently to ResNet-50 in Recipes B and F to keep validation comparable across encoder families. As a result, validation and test metrics from Recipes B/F and Recipe S are not numerically interchangeable; only Recipe S can be used to make direct claims of reproduction fidelity against [10].

e) Augmentation pipeline: Recipe S disables wav-level augmentation entirely (no volume perturbation, no additive noise) and applies SpecAugment with rate 1.0 on every sample, using a smaller frequency mask of 7 and time mask of 50. Recipes B and F instead activate light wav-level augmentation (volume modulation and additive Gaussian noise, each at rate 0.2) and reduce the SpecAugment application rate to 0.8 with a larger $freq.mask = 10$ and $timemask = 50$ as described in Appendix G. The rationale is to introduce diversity earlier in the augmentation chain (at the waveform level) rather than relying exclusively on the spectrogram-level masking that Schachinger employs.

f) Spectrogram normalisation and tensor layout: Recipe S does not apply per-feature mean–std normalisation of the log-Mel spectrogram and uses the BCFT tensor layout (Batch, Channel, Frequency, Time). Recipes B and F apply mean–std normalisation using the dataset statistics ($\mu = -3.09$, $\sigma = 4.82$) and use the BCTF layout, as described in Chapter IV and Appendix G.

g) Classification-head architecture: Both Recipe S and Recipes B/F use a three-layer head before the final classifier. Recipe S uses [2048, 512, 256] (hard-coded for the ResNet-50 embedding dimension of 2048). Recipes B and F use [embedding dim., 512, 256], where embedding dim. is adapted to the encoder (2048 for ResNet-50, 768 for ViT-Base); the head is therefore architecturally equivalent for ResNet-50 and adapted only in the input dimension for ViT-Base.

h) Early stopping: Recipe S requires *all* of validation loss, accuracy, and macro-F1 to satisfy the patience criterion (`require_all`), with patience 7 and `min_delta = 0`. Recipes B and F monitor only macro-F1 with patience 15 and `min_delta = 0.005`. The B/F setup aligns the early-stopping signal directly with the primary evaluation metric and avoids premature termination caused by noisy auxiliary metrics, particularly the unweighted accuracy, which is dominated by the two majority classes and therefore not a reliable proxy for macro-F1 on this dataset. Schachinger applies the early-stopping patience counter to multiple metrics simultaneously and resets it whenever any of the three tracked metrics improves; training can therefore be artificially extended beyond the point at which macro-F1 has plateaued. Each additional criterion provides another opportunity for random validation-set fluctuations to trigger an additional training window [28].

i) Statistical evaluation: Recipe S is run with a single fixed seed (96). Recipes B and F are evaluated across 10 independent seeds, following the multi-seed evaluation principle of Bouthillier *et al.* [29].

Parameter	Value
Sample rate	32 kHz
Spectrogram type	Log-Mel spectrogram
Mel filterbanks	128
FFT size	2048
Hop length	512
Amplitude scale	Decibel (dB)
Normalisation	Dataset-wise mean and standard deviation ($\mu = -3.09$, $\sigma = 4.82$)
Tensor orientation	BCTF (Batch \times Channel \times Time \times Frequency)
Crop duration	7 s (pretraining) / 15 s (fine-tuning)
Fixed frame size	448 (pretraining) / 944 (fine-tuning)

TABLE XX: Audio frontend configuration applied uniformly across all training runs. The log-Mel spectrogram is converted to decibel scale and then standardised using dataset-level statistics computed once on the full dataset and reused identically during pretraining and fine-tuning. The crop duration and corresponding fixed frame size are the only parameters that differ between pretraining and fine-tuning.

APPENDIX G AUGMENTATION PIPELINE

Pretraining is done on batches of spectrograms with shape $[B, 1, 448, 128]$ with a crop duration of 7s. The fixed frame size of 448 was chosen to yield a grid of 28×8 non-overlapping patches when used with a patch size of 16×16 , as applied in all ViT-based pretraining configurations.

The supervised fine-tuning configuration uses a longer crop duration of 15s, corresponding to 944 time frames and a patch grid of 59×8 for ViT-based encoders. This increase is empirically motivated: [10] systematically evaluated crop durations and reported that reducing the segment length from 15s to 7s on the supervised ADSiM dataset caused a substantial macro-F1 degradation (0.929 \rightarrow 0.848). Table XX summarizes the uniform audio frontend.

A key design decision across all pipelines using Recipes B and F (Appendix F) is the adoption of the BCTF tensor orientation as described in Section V-A.

The choice of BCTF is motivated by compatibility with ViT pretrained checkpoints. When loading pretrained weights from these sources, adopting the same orientation avoids the need for positional-embedding transposition or re-interpolation across different aspect ratios.

The augmentation pipeline operates in two stages: waveform-level augmentations are applied first, followed by spectrogram-level augmentations after Mel-spectrogram computation.

At the waveform level, random temporal cropping to the target duration of 15s is applied (with zero-padding for shorter recordings), alongside volume modulation with probability 0.2 (bidirectional, maximum change of 5%) and additive Gaussian noise with probability 0.2 (additive volume factor 0.1, noise factor 0.004).

At the spectrogram level, SpecAugment [40] is applied with frequency masking (`freq_mask_param` = 10 Mel bins) and

time masking (`time_mask_param` = 50 frames), each with probability 0.8.

Validation and test sets use centre cropping with zero-padding (uniform mode) instead of random cropping, ensuring deterministic and reproducible evaluation. All stochastic augmentations are disabled during validation and testing, mirroring inference-time conditions and ensuring that the monitored validation metric reflects the model’s true generalisation performance.

APPENDIX H ViT ENCODER SELECTION

The primary encoder used throughout this work is **ViT-Base** [12]. This appendix documents the preliminary experiment underlying that choice, in which ViT-Small (~ 22 M parameters) and ViT-Base (~ 86 M parameters) were compared across five matched configurations.

Two considerations motivated the comparison. First, model size trades capacity against the risk of overfitting on the small ADSiM labeled set, making the smaller encoder a plausible alternative. Second, the publicly available AudioSet AudioMAE checkpoints are released only at the Base scale [14]; selecting ViT-Small would therefore have precluded the AudioSet transfer-learning track entirely.

Both encoders were evaluated under identical pretraining and fine-tuning settings (Chapter IV), using the same number of pretraining epochs and the same batch size, and reported following the evaluation procedure of Section VI-B. Five configurations were evaluated: the supervised baseline $V-B$ (random initialisation, no SSL); MAE pretraining on ADSiM $V-M$ (epoch 85) and its ImageNet-continued variant $V-M-IM$ (epoch 30); and Contrastive Triplet pretraining on ADSiM $V-C$ (epoch 150) and its ImageNet-continued variant $V-C-IM$ (epoch 80). Pretraining epochs are listed for reproducibility.

Table XXI reports the downstream results. On macro-F1, ViT-Base wins 4/5 configurations, the sole exception being $V-M-IM$. On mAP it wins 3/5, with $V-C-IM$ and $V-M$ favouring ViT-Small by small margins (0.2 and 0.4 pp). The supervised baseline $V-B$ points in the same direction, favouring ViT-Base on both metrics from random initialisation.

Given the small number of paired comparisons, no formal test is conducted and the conclusion follows the qualitative trend. The macro-F1 advantage of ViT-Base is consistent across configurations and, apart from $V-M-IM$, extends to mAP, in line with the model-size scaling reported in AudioMAE [14]. ViT-Base is therefore selected as the primary encoder for the core experiments.

APPENDIX I PRETRAINING BATCH SIZE

This appendix reports a complementary investigation into the effect of the pretraining batch size on two of the SSL configurations evaluated in this work ($V-C-IM$ and $V-M-AS$). The investigation is reported in the appendix rather than in the main text, because the underlying premise: that batch size could be a leading hyperparameter for the SSL frameworks

Configuration	ViT-Small	ViT-Base
V-B	79.4	80.4
V-C	80.1	81.6
V-C-IM	81.6	83.5
V-M	81.9	84.2
V-M-IM	82.8	82.5

(a) Primary metric: macro-F1 (%).

Configuration	ViT-Small	ViT-Base
V-B	93.5	94.2
V-C	94.4	94.6
V-C-IM	95.8	95.6
V-M	96.1	95.7
V-M-IM	94.8	95.2

(b) Secondary metric: mean average precision (%).

TABLE XXI: Downstream results for ViT-Small and ViT-Base across the five preliminary configurations. Best per row in bold. Values follow the reporting convention of Section VI-B (cross-split median).

Fig. 22: Pretraining loss for the ViT-Small encoder. Left: MAE initialisation comparison (random vs. continued from ImageNet). Right: Contrastive Triplet initialisation comparison (random vs. continued from ImageNet). Convergence is comparable to ViT-Base (Section VI-D), indicating that both encoder sizes followed similar optimisation trends during pretraining.

Fig. 23: (left) Audio-MAE pretraining loss batch-size comparison (32 vs. 96) for V-M-AS. (right) Contrastive triplet pretraining loss batch-size comparison (32 vs. 48 triplets) for V-C-IM.

used in this work does not hold for either framework. The Audio-MAE objective is reconstruction-based and does not depend on in-batch comparisons of any kind, and the contrastive triplet pipeline samples negatives globally from the unlabeled dataset rather than from within the batch (see Section IV-B). Chapter VIII discusses why batch size is therefore not a meaningful leading hyperparameter in this work and how this differs from the SimCLR setup [24]. The data reported below confirm the expectation that follows from this argument empirically.

a) Setup: For the two best-converging ViT configurations (V-M-AS and V-C-IM), additional pretraining runs at the hardware-limit batch size were conducted: V-C-IM (32 \rightarrow 48 triplets) and V-M-AS (32 \rightarrow 96). All other settings match the corresponding entries in Table XV and Table XVI.

b) Pretraining convergence: Figures 23 show the pretraining-loss curves under the two batch sizes.

The two frameworks behave differently in the pretraining loss. For V-M-AS, increasing the batch size from 32 to 96 leads to a faster and slightly lower-converging reconstruction loss. For V-C-IM, increasing the batch size from 32 to 48 triplets does not reduce the contrastive triplet loss; the trajectories overlap.

c) Downstream effect (best-checkpoint): To remain consistent with the best-checkpoint protocol used in this work, the comparison fixes the checkpoint to the best cross-split checkpoint determined under the batch-size-32 setup, and

Fig. 24: Cross-split macro-F1 (median with IQR) of the V-M-AS configurations as a function of pretraining epoch, comparing batch sizes.

evaluates that same checkpoint against its larger-batch-size counterpart ($n = 20$ per condition). Two tests per metric, Bonferroni-corrected with $\alpha_{\text{Bonf}} = 0.025$.

d) Learning curves: Figures 24 and 25 show the cross-split macro-F1 and mAP (median with IQR) of the two configurations as a function of pretraining epoch, with the batch sizes overlaid.

e) Reading: Under the best-checkpoint protocol, none of the four downstream comparisons reaches the Bonferroni-corrected threshold. The point-estimate differences are within 0.2 pp on both metrics for both configurations. The strongest signal is the V-M-AS mAP point estimate ($d = -0.70$, $p = 0.034$), which sits just above the corrected threshold of $\alpha_{\text{Bonf}} = 0.025$ and is not significant under the prespecified Bonferroni correction.

The empirical pattern is consistent with the structural argument: neither pretraining objective is bottlenecked by the

Comparison	Metric	Default BS (%)	Larger BS (%)	Δ (pp)	Cohen’s d	p
V-C-IM, 32 \rightarrow 48	macro-F1	83.5	83.5	0.0	−0.03	0.932 (n.s.)
	mAP	95.6	95.5	−0.1	−0.21	0.512 (n.s.)
V-M-AS, 32 \rightarrow 96	macro-F1	87.3	87.3	0.0	−0.03	0.932 (n.s.)
	mAP	96.4	96.2	−0.2	−0.70	0.034 (n.s.)

TABLE XXII: Effect of pretraining batch size on downstream performance, evaluated on the best cross-split checkpoint selected under the batch-size-32 setup. Δ is reported as larger batch size minus default. Bonferroni-corrected $\alpha_{\text{Bonf}} = 0.025$.

Fig. 25: Cross-split mAP (median with IQR) of the V-C-IM configurations as a function of pretraining epoch, comparing batch sizes.

batch size in a way that propagates into downstream performance. The contrastive triplet objective is decoupled from the batch size by construction (global negative sampling, see Section IV-B), and although the Audio-MAE pretraining loss does converge faster at the larger batch size, this advantage does not translate into a downstream improvement. The wall-clock advantage of the larger batch size therefore remains the relevant practical consideration for choosing a batch size on this task.

APPENDIX J

COMPLEMENTARY EXPERIMENT: RECIPE EFFECT

This appendix reports a complementary recipe-effect data point that is referenced by the main-text recipe comparison in Section VI-H but is not part of that section, because it differs methodologically from the two best-checkpoint t -test comparisons reported there.

a) Motivation: The two main-text comparisons in Section VI-H hold the encoder fixed (R-C and V-M-AS, respectively) and switch the downstream recipe. They show that Recipe S is favourable on the ResNet-50 encoder R-C and that Recipe F is favourable on the ViT-Base encoder V-M-AS. To strengthen the recipe-encoder coupling reading, a third data point is desirable: switching the recipe on a *second* ResNet-50 encoder, namely the one trained under [10] pretraining regime in Section VI-C. If Recipe S is favourable on that encoder as well, the recipe-encoder coupling reading is supported on both ResNet-50 cases examined in this work.

b) Setup and comparison protocol: The encoder pre-trained for the reproduction in Section VI-C was fine-tuned under Recipe F with 10 seeds across 2 splits ($n = 20$). The Recipe S reference for the same encoder is the cross-split Finetuning sample reported in Section VI-C (20 unseeded runs

Recipe	macro-F1 (%)	n
Recipe S	90.6	40
Recipe F	66.8	20

TABLE XXIII: The ResNet-50 encoder used in Section VI-C for the reproduction of [10] under two downstream recipes. Cross-split medians. No t -test is reported; the two samples follow different seed protocols.

per split across 2 splits, $n = 40$). The two samples differ in their seed protocol and a t -test on samples obtained under different seed protocols is not meaningful. The comparison is therefore reported as a median-level descriptive contrast only.

c) Result: The median macro-F1 of the reproduction encoder drops by 23.8 pp when Recipe S is replaced by Recipe F. The direction is consistent with Comparison 1 of Section VI-H, where switching from Recipe F to Recipe S on the R-C encoder improves macro-F1 by +7.2 pp. Taken together, both ResNet-50 encoders examined in this work are favoured by Recipe S over Recipe F, while the only ViT-Base encoder examined under both recipes (V-M-AS) is favoured by Recipe F.

d) Caveat: The drop on the reproduction encoder (−23.8 pp) substantially exceeds the Recipe F→Recipe S gain observed on R-C (+7.2 pp), but the two magnitudes cannot be compared literally for two reasons. First, the contrast reported here is a median-level descriptive comparison under heterogeneous seed protocols, not a t -test under a shared protocol. Second, the reproduction encoder was pre-trained under the paradigm associated with Recipe S and is therefore expected to be more tightly coupled to it than the R-C encoder, which was pre-trained under the recipe of this work. The −23.8 pp should accordingly be read as a *direction-consistent* indication of the recipe-encoder coupling rather than a calibrated effect-size estimate.

APPENDIX K

TRAINING ENVIRONMENT

All experiments were conducted on one NVIDIA RTX 4090 GPU.